

Master Thesis

Flow modeling and control employing dynamic mode decomposition and deep reinforcement learning

submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree
"Master of Science in Computational Modeling and Simulation"

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submission date

18.12.2025

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Kurzfassung

Strömungsmodellierung und -kontrolle mittels Dynamic Mode Decomposition und Deep Reinforcement Learning

Die hohe Dimensionalität von Strömungssimulationen stellt hinsichtlich Rechenaufwand und Speicherverbrauch eine große Herausforderung dar, was die Entwicklung von Modellierungstechniken mit reduzierter Ordnung erforderlich macht. Die dynamische Moduserlegung mit Steuerung (DMDc) ist eine solche Technik, die einen Rahmen für die Approximation der zeitlichen Entwicklung des Strömungszustands unter Berücksichtigung der Strömungssteuerung bietet. In dieser Arbeit wird DMDc als Ersatzmodell verwendet, um die Optimierung von Steuerungsgesetzen in Anwendungen zur aktiven Strömungssteuerung im geschlossenen Regelkreis unter Verwendung von Deep Reinforcement Learning zu beschleunigen. Um Speicherbeschränkungen bei groß angelegten Strömungsproblemen zu bewältigen, wird ein partitionierter Singulärwertzerlegungsalgorithmus verwendet, um eine speichereffiziente DMDc-Modellkonstruktion zu ermöglichen. Insgesamt zielt dieses Projekt darauf ab, den Rechenaufwand und die Durchlaufzeit von Strömungssimulationen zu reduzieren und gleichzeitig die Speicherbeschränkungen bei der datengesteuerten Strömungsmodellierung und -steuerung zu verringern.

Abstract

Flow modeling and control employing dynamic mode decomposition and deep reinforcement learning

The high dimensionality of fluid flow simulations poses significant challenges in terms of computational cost and memory usage, motivating the development of reduced-order modeling techniques. Dynamic Mode Decomposition with Control (DMDc) is one such technique that provides a framework for approximating the time evolution of the flow state while accounting for flow actuation. In this work, DMDc is used as a surrogate model to accelerate the optimization of control laws in closed-loop active flow control applications using deep reinforcement learning. To address memory limitations in large-scale flow problems, a partitioned singular value decomposition algorithm is employed to enable memory-efficient DMDc model construction. Overall, this project aims to reduce the computational cost and turnaround time of flow simulations while alleviating memory constraints in data-driven flow modeling and control.

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List of Symbols

Latin symbols	Units	Meaning
A	-	Linear evolution operator
B	-	Control input operator
<i>b</i>	-	Batch size
<i>C_d</i>	-	Drag coefficient
<i>C_l</i>	-	Lift coefficient
D	-	Singular value matrix
<i>d</i>	m	Cylinder diameter
<i>m</i>	-	State dimension
<i>n</i>	-	Number of snapshots
<i>n_{shuf}</i>	-	Shuffling rate
<i>p</i>	Pa	Pressure field
<i>Re</i>	-	Reynolds number
<i>R</i>	-	Reward
<i>u</i>	m/s	Velocity
<i>s</i>	-	Number of partitions
<i>\tilde{t}</i>	-	Convective time (CTU)
U	-	Left singular vector matrix
<i>U</i>	-	Common POD basis
<i>U</i>	m/s	Velocity field
u	-	Control input vector
V	-	Right singular vector matrix
X	-	Snapshot matrix
x	-	State vector

Greek symbols	Units	Meaning
ω	rad/s	Angular velocity
Φ	-	DMD modes
η	-	Snapshot truncation rank
κ	-	DMDc truncation rank

Indexes	Meaning
pred	Predicted values
ref	Reference values
train	Training data
test	Testing data
r	Truncation rank

Other symbols	Meaning
$\ \cdot\ _2$	Euclidean norm
$\ \cdot\ _F$	Frobenius norm
$(\cdot)^T$	Transpose
$(\cdot)^\dagger$	Moore–Penrose pseudoinverse

Acronyms	Meaning
AFC	Active flow control
CFD	Computational fluid dynamics
CTU	Convective time units
DMD	Dynamic mode decomposition
DMDc	Dynamic mode decomposition with control
HPC	High performance computing
MF-DRL	Model-free deep reinforcement learning
ML	Machine learning
MORS	Multi-operator random shuffling
MPI	Message passing interface
POD	Proper orthogonal decomposition
PPO	Proximal policy optimization
ROM	Reduced order modeling
SVD	Singular value decomposition

1. Introduction

Active Flow Control (AFC) remains one of the most challenging and widely studied problems in fluid mechanics. It aims to improve flow behavior by modifying the flow field through controlled actuation. Numerous studies have focused on drag reduction, vortex-shedding suppression, and lift optimization [26]. Some widely used actuation mechanisms for AFC include synthetic jets, plasma actuators, or moving control surfaces. Over the years, substantial effort has also been devoted to designing effective control laws, such as Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) control, Linear Feedback Controllers, and Model Predictive Control.

1.1. State of the art

With the rapid progress of machine learning (ML), new AFC strategies have emerged. Among these, Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) has shown great promise, as it enables the learning of nonlinear and state-dependent control laws directly from data [25]. This is particularly useful for fluid flow control problems, which are inherently nonlinear and high-dimensional due to the governing Navier-Stokes equations. The general concept of DRL-based AFC is illustrated in Fig. 1.1. In this framework, two main components form the control loop: the *DRL agent* and the *environment*. The agent acts as the controller and learns a mapping between the system's state and the optimal actuation required to achieve the control objective. This mapping, called the *policy*, is typically represented by a neural network. To train it, the agent interacts with the *environment*, which is the underlying physical or numerical system that evolves in response to the applied *action*. Starting from an initially random policy, the agent receives a *reward* that quantifies how well the objective is achieved, and updates the policy accordingly. Over many iterations, this process yields an improved control law.

The *environment* plays a central role, advancing the flow state over time in response to the agent's actuation and providing the resulting observations and rewards. Although experimental setups can serve as environments, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations are more commonly used due to their controllability, repeatability, and ability to generate large amounts of training data. DRL frameworks that rely solely on direct interaction with such CFD environments are referred to as *model-free* DRL (MF-DRL) methods.

Despite significant advances in CFD-based DRL, computational cost remains a major bottleneck, especially for practical problems such as vehicle aerodynamics or turbulent flows [9]. Font et al. [5] demonstrated DRL-based control of a turbulent separation bubble on a flat plate using Large-Eddy Simulations. The training required 144 hours (6 days) on 8 GPUs, corresponding to 1152 GPU-hours.

Suárez et al. [23] reported a drag reduction of approximately 9% for turbulent flow past a 3D cylinder using DRL. The total training time was around 2 weeks on 11,520 CPU cores, totaling roughly 3 million CPU hours. These examples illustrate that the computational effort required for DRL-based AFC increases dramatically as problem complexity increases. MF-DRL methods are characterized by very high computational costs due to the large number of CFD simulations required. A natural next step is the use of *model-based* reinforcement learning, where a surrogate model of the environment is trained, usually using neural networks, and subsequently used to accelerate policy learning. For instance, [29] demonstrated training-time reductions of approximately 65% for 2D cylinder flow and up to 80% for the more complex fluidic pinball configuration.

Training costs can be further reduced by replacing the CFD environment with a reduced-order model (ROM). Dynamic Mode Decomposition with control (DMDc) provides a suitable framework for learning linear reduced-order models that predict flow evolution under actuation inputs. Sakamoto and Okabayashi [22] implemented this idea and reported significant computational savings. However, their approach relied on Q-learning, which is not the most optimal method for policy update, and the accuracy of the DMDc model was limited.

Figure 1.1.: Framework for active flow control using deep reinforcement learning. The image is taken from [21] and then edited.

1.2. Present work

This thesis aims to develop a robust reduced-order model based on Dynamic Mode Decomposition with control (DMDc) to serve as an environment in place of a CFD solver. The target configuration is the flow past a 2D cylinder (see Chapter 3), for which a library of actuation signals is generated (see Sec. 5.1), and corresponding DMDc models are fitted. Several strategies are explored to improve the robustness of the DMDc framework's predictions. These include constructing a model library (see Sec. 5.3), introducing time-delay embeddings to enhance model stability, and investigating selection strategies such as randomly switching between models within the library.

A key step in constructing DMDc models is computing the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) of the snapshot matrix. To accommodate higher-dimensional datasets, the Partitioned SVD algorithm with online eigen-learning is implemented (see Chapter 4). While this approach is not essential for the relatively simple case considered here, it establishes a foundation for future work on more complex flow scenarios.

Once the DMDc models are constructed, they are integrated into the *drlfoam* framework [17], replacing the CFD solver with the reduced-order model (see Chapter 6). To enable this integration, additional components for lift and drag evaluation (see Sec. 4.2.1), and pressure prediction at probe locations, are developed. Finally, the ROM-based approach is compared against the traditional model-free DRL method to evaluate how well the ROM-based framework performs in practice.

2. Theory

2.1. Partitioned Singular Value Decomposition

Partitioned singular value decomposition provides an efficient strategy for computing the SVD of large data matrices. Here, the split-and-merge approach proposed by Liang et al. [12] is adopted. This method overcomes both memory and computational limitations in large-scale data analysis. The general idea is to partition the data into smaller blocks and apply standard SVD algorithms to each block separately. After which, the results are merged. The following sections describe the theoretical background.

2.1.1. Singular Value Decomposition

SVD is a fundamental tool in linear algebra. It forms the basis of many data-driven techniques such as dynamic mode decomposition (DMD), proper orthogonal decomposition (POD), and principal component analysis among others. These methods are valuable when working with high-dimensional data which often arises in the study of complex systems. For example, climate datasets may include temperature, pressure, and wind fields at both spatial and temporal scales. In such cases, a few dominant patterns often govern the dynamics [2]. This allows high-dimensional data to be approximated in a much lower-dimensional space. In the climate example, these structures can correspond to modes such as El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO), a dominant ocean-atmosphere pattern that strongly influences the global climate variations.

A similar phenomenon occurs in fluid dynamics. Capturing the turbulent wake behind a bluff body typically requires high-fidelity simulations, involving millions or even billions of degrees of freedom. Yet the flow is often dominated by coherent structures such as periodic vortex shedding. In order to compute these coherent structures using SVD, the input usually consists of velocity and pressure fields. The decomposition, then yields low-dimensional representations that capture the flow's essential dynamics. Formally, the data matrix is constructed as $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$

$$\mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{n-1} \end{bmatrix}^T. \quad (2.1)$$

The columns $\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbb{R}^m$ represent data from simulations or experiments. These may be flattened pressure fields, velocity fields, or a concatenation of both. The index k denotes the k -th measurement. In fluid flows, k typically indexes time. Each column then corresponds to a system snapshot at a specific instant. Thus, the columns capture spatial variation, while the rows correspond to temporal variation. Usually, the spatial dimension m is much larger than the number of snapshots n ,

making the matrix tall and skinny.

Economy SVD

For tall and skinny matrices $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ with $m \geq n$, the singular value decomposition can be written directly in its *economy* form as

$$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{V}^T, \quad (2.2)$$

where $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ and $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ are orthogonal matrices whose columns are the left and right singular vectors, respectively, and $\mathbf{D} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is a diagonal matrix containing the non-negative singular values. The operator $(\cdot)^T$ denotes the transpose.

Since there are at most n non-zero singular values, the economy SVD provides an exact representation of \mathbf{X} while avoiding the storage of zero-valued components present in the full decomposition. This formulation therefore significantly reduces the memory requirements.

Truncated SVD

It is also possible to construct a low-rank approximation of the snapshot matrix using the SVD. The singular values indicate the relative importance of each mode and in many cases they decay rapidly. Indicating that the first few modes contain most of the information. Those beyond a certain index r are negligibly small and can be discarded, yielding a much smaller rank- r approximation. This is particularly useful in complex systems whose behavior can be represented by a few dominant coherent structures. The truncated SVD is defined as

$$\underset{\mathbf{X}_r \text{ s.t. } \text{rank}(\mathbf{X}_r)=r}{\text{argmin}} \|\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{X}_r\|_2^2 = \mathbf{U}_r \mathbf{D}_r \mathbf{V}_r^T, \quad (2.3)$$

where $\mathbf{U}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times r}$, $\mathbf{V}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$, and $\mathbf{D}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$.

2.1.2. Split and Merge algorithm

The split-and-merge algorithm proposed by Liang et al. [12] provides a strategic approach for computing the SVD of large matrices. The underlying procedure for computing the SVD itself is not altered; rather, standard off-the-shelf SVD algorithms are applied in a structured manner to significantly improve performance.

The central concept of the split-and-merge algorithm is to partition a large matrix into s smaller submatrices, compute the SVD of each partition independently, and then combine the results through numerical manipulations to obtain the SVD of the original matrix. The primary motivation to use

this approach is memory efficiency. By partitioning the data matrix into smaller blocks, neither the full snapshot matrix nor the individual SVDs needs to be stored in memory at any point. The performance of the algorithm can also be assessed in terms of computational complexity, which is commonly estimated by counting the required floating-point operations (FLOPs). To fully assess the benefit of the split-and-merge approach, it is also useful to consider the *time complexity*, which reflects the actual runtime. Unlike FLOP counts, time complexity is influenced by factors such as parallelization, memory access patterns, and operations with negligible computational costs (such as multiplications by zero).

Formulation

The split-and-merge algorithm is particularly beneficial when the number of rows m of the data matrix is much larger than the number of columns n . Consider a matrix $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, which is partitioned row-wise into s blocks of approximately equal size,

$$\mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}_1, \mathbf{X}_2, \dots, \mathbf{X}_s \end{bmatrix}^T. \quad (2.4)$$

In practice, for example in OpenFOAM simulations, domain decomposition naturally provides such a partitioning. The number of partitions corresponds to the number of parallel domain decompositions via the Message Passing Interface (MPI), commonly referred to as MPI ranks. Next, the SVD of each block is computed independently,

$$\mathbf{X}_i = \mathbf{U}_i \mathbf{D}_i \mathbf{V}_i^T, \quad i = 1, \dots, s. \quad (2.5)$$

These SVD computations may be carried out sequentially or in parallel.

The results are merged by first computing $\mathbf{D}_i \mathbf{V}_i^T$ for each partition and concatenating them row-wise to form the matrix

$$\mathbf{Y} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{D}_1 \mathbf{V}_1^T, \mathbf{D}_2 \mathbf{V}_2^T, \dots, \mathbf{D}_s \mathbf{V}_s^T \end{bmatrix}^T, \quad (2.6)$$

where $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{s \cdot n \times n}$. Since $s \cdot n \ll m$ in typical applications, computing the SVD of \mathbf{Y} is significantly less expensive than computing the SVD of \mathbf{X} directly. Then the SVD of the matrix \mathbf{Y} is computed as,

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{U}_y \mathbf{D}_y \mathbf{V}_y^T. \quad (2.7)$$

To recover the SVD of the original matrix, define the block-diagonal matrix.

$$\bar{\mathbf{U}} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{U}_1, \mathbf{U}_2, \dots, \mathbf{U}_s).$$

It follows that

$$\mathbf{X} = \overline{\mathbf{U}}\mathbf{Y} = \overline{\mathbf{U}}\mathbf{U}_y\mathbf{D}_y\mathbf{V}_y^T. \quad (2.8)$$

Hence, the SVD of \mathbf{X} can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{U} &= \overline{\mathbf{U}}\mathbf{U}_y, \\ \mathbf{D} &= \mathbf{D}_y, \\ \mathbf{V} &= \mathbf{V}_y. \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

In practice, to avoid storing the entire $\overline{\mathbf{U}}$ matrix in memory, and also avoid unnecessary multiplications with zero blocks, the left singular matrix \mathbf{U} is constructed in compact form as

$$\mathbf{U} = \left[\mathbf{U}_1\mathbf{U}_{y1}, \mathbf{U}_2\mathbf{U}_{y2}, \dots, \mathbf{U}_s\mathbf{U}_{ys} \right]^T, \quad (2.10)$$

where \mathbf{U}_i denotes the i -th block in $\overline{\mathbf{U}}$, and \mathbf{U}_{yi} is the sub-matrix of \mathbf{U}_y formed from the corresponding row block $((i-1) \cdot n) : i \cdot n$ [13].

The construction of these matrices and their operations is illustrated in Fig. 2.1, where zero blocks indicate computations that can be skipped. Finally, the decomposition may be *truncated* to a prescribed rank r by retaining only the r leading singular values in \mathbf{D}_y and the corresponding columns of \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{V} . This truncated form further reduces storage and computational cost while preserving the dominant structures of the data. A step-by-step implementation is summarized in Algorithm 1.

Complexity analysis

The time complexity of the partitioned SVD algorithm is reduced in both parallel and serial implementations when the number of partitions s is chosen appropriately with respect to the matrix size. Liang et al. [12] demonstrate that, in the parallel case, if s is selected such that $s < m/n$, where m and n denote the number of rows and columns, respectively, then the computational time is always lower compared to the standard SVD.

In the serial setting, performance gains are still achieved provided that s lies within a certain admissible range, which can be determined by solving an inequality parameterized by the aspect ratio m/n . For example, Liang et al. [12] report that when $m/n = 10$, one may choose $2 \leq s \leq 4$, whereas for $m/n = 100$, the inequality is satisfied for $2 \leq s \leq 67$.

A significant advantage of the partitioned SVD is its lower memory requirements. Constructing the full data matrix may require tens of gigabytes of memory, and in large-scale CFD simulations of vehicles, the memory footprint can even exceed the capacity of entire compute clusters [13].

Partitioning alleviates this problem by reducing the memory needed to construct and process each sub-matrix, making the approach feasible for otherwise intractable large-scale problems.

Algorithm 1: Split-and-Merge SVD (row partitioning), adapted from Liang et al. [12]

Input : $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, number of partitions s , truncation rank r

Output: $\mathbf{U}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times r}$, $\mathbf{D}_r \in \mathbb{R}^r$, $\mathbf{V}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$.

1. Partition rows: $\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{X}_1, \dots, \mathbf{X}_s]^\top$, with $\mathbf{X}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{m_i \times n}$ and $\sum_i m_i = m$.

2. Compute local SVDs and truncate:

for $i = 1$ **to** s **do**

 Compute SVD of \mathbf{X}_i and truncate to rank r , to get the decomposition $\mathbf{U}_{r,i} \in \mathbb{R}^{m_i \times r}$,

$\mathbf{D}_{r,i} \in \mathbb{R}^r$, $\mathbf{V}_{r,i} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$.

end

3. Construct stacked matrix:

$$\mathbf{Y} = [\mathbf{D}_{r,1} \mathbf{V}_{r,1}^\top, \mathbf{D}_{r,2} \mathbf{V}_{r,2}^\top, \dots, \mathbf{D}_{r,s} \mathbf{V}_{r,s}^\top]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{s \cdot r \times n}.$$

4. Global SVD on Y and truncate: Compute SVD of \mathbf{Y} and truncate to rank r to get the decomposition $\mathbf{U}_{r,y} \in \mathbb{R}^{(s \cdot r) \times r}$, $\mathbf{D}_{r,y} \in \mathbb{R}^r$, $\mathbf{V}_{r,y} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$.

5. Compute \mathbf{U}_r : For each i , define the row-block $\mathbf{U}_{r,y}^{(i)} \leftarrow \mathbf{U}_{r,y}[(i-1) \cdot r : i \cdot r]$ and set

$$\mathbf{U}_r = [\mathbf{U}_{r,1} \mathbf{U}_{r,y}^{(1)}, \mathbf{U}_{r,2} \mathbf{U}_{r,y}^{(2)}, \dots, \mathbf{U}_{r,s} \mathbf{U}_{r,y}^{(s)}]^\top.$$

6. Return: The truncated SVD decomposition of the data matrix $(\mathbf{U}_r, \mathbf{D}_{r,y}, \mathbf{V}_{r,y})$.

2.1.3. Online Eigen-Learning

The split-and-merge algorithm can also be extended to streaming data, as proposed by Liang et al. [12]. In this case, the SVD is computed incrementally, reusing information from previous computations to reduce overall computational cost. Such an approach is particularly useful in real-time applications, for example, in flow monitoring, where sensor measurements arrive continuously, and the number of snapshots increases over time.

Formulation

The online extension of the split-and-merge algorithm applies the same principles recursively to streaming data. The goal is to incrementally update the SVD of the full matrix using information from previously computed factors, thereby avoiding recomputation from scratch.

The data arrives in batches, the data of the t -th batch is denoted by \mathbf{X}_t and the data matrix up to

the t -th batch is given by $\mathbf{X}_{1:t} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n_1}$. When a new batch $\mathbf{X}_{t+1} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n_2}$ arrives, the SVD of the augmented matrix $\mathbf{X}_{1:t+1} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times (n_1+n_2)}$ is evaluated incrementally by making use of the previously computed SVD of $\mathbf{X}_{1:t}$.

First, the SVD of the new batch is computed using split-and-merge approach:

$$\mathbf{X}_{t+1} = \mathbf{U}_{t+1} \mathbf{D}_{t+1} \mathbf{V}_{t+1}^\top. \quad (2.11)$$

where $\mathbf{U}_{t+1} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n_2}$, $\mathbf{D}_{t+1} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_2 \times n_2}$, and $\mathbf{V}_{t+1} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_2 \times n_2}$. The singular value decomposition (SVD) of the snapshot matrix $\mathbf{X}_{1:t}$ is already known and is given by

$$\mathbf{X}_{1:t} = \mathbf{U}_{1:t} \mathbf{D}_{1:t} \mathbf{V}_{1:t}^\top, \quad (2.12)$$

where $\mathbf{U}_{1:t} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n_1}$, $\mathbf{D}_{1:t} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1 \times n_1}$, and $\mathbf{V}_{1:t} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1 \times n_1}$. Next, the block-diagonal matrix $\bar{\mathbf{V}}$ is constructed as

$$\bar{\mathbf{V}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{V}_{1:t} & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{V}_{t+1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2.13)$$

where $\mathbf{V}_{1:t} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1 \times n_1}$, $\mathbf{V}_{t+1} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_2 \times n_2}$, and $\bar{\mathbf{V}} \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_1+n_2) \times (n_1+n_2)}$. Then, the matrix \mathbf{W} is written as

$$\mathbf{W} = [\mathbf{U}_{1:t} \mathbf{D}_{1:t} \quad \mathbf{U}_{t+1} \mathbf{D}_{t+1}]. \quad (2.14)$$

where $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times (n_1+n_2)}$. The augmented data matrix can now be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{X}_{1:t+1} &= [\mathbf{X}_{1:t} \quad \mathbf{X}_{t+1}] \\ &= [\mathbf{U}_{1:t} \mathbf{D}_{1:t} \quad \mathbf{U}_{t+1} \mathbf{D}_{t+1}] \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{V}_{1:t}^\top & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{V}_{t+1}^\top \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \mathbf{W} \bar{\mathbf{V}}^\top. \end{aligned} \quad (2.15)$$

At this stage, the SVD of \mathbf{W} is computed using

$$\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{U}_w \mathbf{D}_w \mathbf{V}_w^\top. \quad (2.16)$$

where $\mathbf{U}_w \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times (n_1+n_2)}$, $\mathbf{D}_w \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_1+n_2) \times (n_1+n_2)}$, and $\mathbf{V}_w \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_1+n_2) \times (n_1+n_2)}$. Although \mathbf{W} has the same dimensions as $\mathbf{X}_{1:t+1}$, the computational benefit arises when using truncation. Specifically, at each incremental step, only the leading r singular values and vectors are retained, with $r \ll n$. Thus, the update matrix $\mathbf{W}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times 2r}$ is much thinner than the full block matrix, enabling efficient online updates. For brevity, the formulation is presented for the full SVD, without rank truncation.

Since $m > n_1 + n_2$, the split-and-merge algorithm is used to compute the SVD of \mathbf{W} . The decomposition of \mathbf{W} is substituted into Eq. (2.15),

$$\mathbf{X}_{1:t+1} = \mathbf{U}_w \mathbf{D}_w \mathbf{V}_w^T \bar{\mathbf{V}}^T = \mathbf{U}_w \mathbf{D}_w (\bar{\mathbf{V}} \mathbf{V}_w)^T. \quad (2.17)$$

Thus, the updated SVD factors of $\mathbf{X}_{1:t+1}$ are identified as ,

$$\mathbf{U}_{1:t+1} = \mathbf{U}_w, \quad \mathbf{D}_{1:t+1} = \mathbf{D}_w, \quad \mathbf{V}_{1:t+1} = \bar{\mathbf{V}} \mathbf{V}_w. \quad (2.18)$$

Since $\bar{\mathbf{V}}$ is block-diagonal, directly forming $\mathbf{V}_{1:t+1}$ can lead to unnecessary multiplications and memory overhead. Instead, it is constructed compactly as,

$$\mathbf{V}_{1:t+1} = [\mathbf{V}_{1:t} \mathbf{V}_w[:, n_1], \mathbf{V}_{t+1} \mathbf{V}_w[n_1 : n_1 + n_2]], \quad (2.19)$$

The procedure is illustrated schematically in Fig. 2.2 and Fig. 2.3, which also highlight the zero blocks where computations can be skipped. In practice, the algorithm explicitly incorporates a rank truncation, retaining only the leading r singular values and corresponding singular vectors at each update step. A step-by-step description of the truncated method is provided in Algorithm. 2.

Algorithm 2: Online Eigen Algorithm for Incremental SVD, adapted from Liang et al. [12]

Input : Streaming batches $\mathbf{X}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{m_t \times n}$, truncation rank r , number of partitions s

Output: Incremental SVD $(\mathbf{U}_{\text{inc}}, \mathbf{D}_{\text{inc}}, \mathbf{V}_{\text{inc}})$

1. Process first batch:

Compute SVD $\mathbf{X}_0 = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{V}^T$ using Algorithm 1.

Initialize $\mathbf{U}_{\text{inc}} \leftarrow \mathbf{U}_r$, $\mathbf{D}_{\text{inc}} \leftarrow \mathbf{D}_r$, $\mathbf{V}_{\text{inc}} \leftarrow \mathbf{V}_r$.

2. Process subsequent batches:

for $t = 1, 2, \dots$ **do**

 Compute truncated SVD of \mathbf{X}_t using Algorithm 1 with s partitions and rank r , yielding $(\mathbf{U}_r, \mathbf{D}_r, \mathbf{V}_r)$.

 Form the concatenated update matrix

$$\mathbf{W}_r = [\mathbf{U}_{\text{inc}} \mathbf{D}_{\text{inc}}, \mathbf{U}_r \mathbf{D}_r].$$

 Compute truncated SVD of \mathbf{W}_r using Algorithm 1 with s partitions and rank r , yielding

$(\mathbf{U}_{r,w}, \mathbf{D}_{r,w}, \mathbf{V}_{r,w})$.

 Update left singular factors:

$\mathbf{U}_{\text{inc}} \leftarrow \mathbf{U}_{r,w}$ $\mathbf{D}_{\text{inc}} \leftarrow \mathbf{D}_{r,w}$

 Update right singular vectors:

$$\mathbf{V}_{\text{inc}} \leftarrow [\mathbf{V}_{\text{inc}}(\mathbf{V}_{r,w})[:, 1:r], \mathbf{V}_r(\mathbf{V}_{r,w})[:, r+1:2r]].$$

end

3. Return:

Incremental SVD $(\mathbf{U}_{\text{inc}}, \mathbf{D}_{\text{inc}}, \mathbf{V}_{\text{inc}})$ after processing all batches.

Figure 2.3.: Schematic showing the matrix operations in the online eigen-learning algorithm. (a) Construction of the intermediate matrix \mathbf{W} , whose SVD yields \mathbf{U}_w , \mathbf{D}_w , and \mathbf{V}_w . These are then used to update the SVD of the full matrix $\mathbf{X}_{1:t+1}$ as $\mathbf{U}_{1:t+1} = \mathbf{U}_w$, $\mathbf{D}_{1:t+1} = \mathbf{D}_w$, and $\mathbf{V}_{1:t+1} = \bar{\mathbf{V}}\mathbf{V}_w$. (b) Multiplication structure used to form $\mathbf{V}_{1:t+1}$ from the block-diagonal matrix $\bar{\mathbf{V}}$ and the right singular vectors \mathbf{V}_w . (c) Final reconstruction of $\mathbf{X}_{1:t+1}$ from the updated SVD components.

2.2. Reduced-Order Modeling

This section outlines the formulation and implementation of the reduced-order models used throughout this study.

2.2.1. Dynamic Mode Decomposition

Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD) is a data-driven technique for extracting spatiotemporal coherent structures from high-dimensional datasets. First, a snapshot matrix \mathbf{X} is constructed as described in Eq. 2.1, where each column $\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbb{R}^m$ represents the system state at the discrete time instant $t_k = k \Delta t$. The time step Δt is assumed to be constant and chosen sufficiently small to resolve the highest frequencies present in the dynamics [1]. Each snapshot thus corresponds to the state of the system at a given time.

The central idea of DMD is to approximate the evolution of the system by a linear operator that advances the state from one time step to the next. Specifically, DMD seeks a matrix \mathbf{A} such that

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x}_k, \quad (2.20)$$

holds in an approximate sense [31]. Since it is generally impossible to identify a single linear operator \mathbf{A} that exactly advances every snapshot, the operator is determined by solving a linear least-squares problem over all pairs of consecutive snapshots.

To this end, the snapshot data are arranged into two time-shifted matrices,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{X}' &= [\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{n-2}], \\ \mathbf{Y} &= [\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{n-1}], \end{aligned} \quad (2.21)$$

where $\mathbf{X}', \mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times (n-1)}$. Mathematically, the least-squares problem is defined as

$$\mathbf{A}^* = \arg \min_{\mathbf{A}} \|\mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{A} \mathbf{X}'\|_F, \quad (2.22)$$

$$\mathbf{A}^* = \mathbf{Y} \mathbf{X}'^\dagger. \quad (2.23)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_F$ denotes the Frobenius norm, and $(\cdot)^\dagger$ denotes the pseudo-inverse. For further details on DMD and its algorithm, the reader is referred to Sec. A.2.

2.2.2. Dynamic Mode Decomposition with Control

Dynamic Mode Decomposition can be extended to systems with control inputs through the DMDc framework introduced by Proctor et al. [19]. The method separates the effects of intrinsic system dynamics from external actuation and yields a reduced-order model capable of predicting the system response under varying control inputs.

In DMDc, the linear state evolution model is augmented to include a control term. Specifically, the state at time step $k + 1$ is approximated as

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{B} \mathbf{u}_k, \quad (2.24)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbb{R}^m$ denotes the system state, $\mathbf{u}_k \in \mathbb{R}^c$ is the control input, $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ is the state-transition operator, and $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times c}$ is the control-input operator.

As in standard DMD, snapshot matrices are constructed from time-resolved data, leading to the state matrices \mathbf{X}' and \mathbf{Y} defined in Sec. 2.21. The corresponding control matrix is given by

$$\mathbf{\Upsilon} = [\mathbf{u}_0, \mathbf{u}_1, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{n-2}]. \quad (2.25)$$

The resulting data equation can be written as

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{X}' + \mathbf{B} \mathbf{\Upsilon}. \quad (2.26)$$

The objective of DMDc is to identify the operators \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} that best fit the data in a least-squares sense. Since both operators are assumed unknown, the state and control data are stacked to form a single linear system,

$$\mathbf{Y} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}' \\ \mathbf{\Upsilon} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{G} \mathbf{Z}, \quad (2.27)$$

where

$$\mathbf{Z} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}' \\ \mathbf{\Upsilon} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(m+c) \times (n-1)}, \quad \mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times (m+c)}. \quad (2.28)$$

The best-fit operator \mathbf{G} is obtained as

$$\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{Y} \mathbf{Z}^\dagger. \quad (2.29)$$

The pseudo-inverse is computed using a truncated SVD of the stacked data matrix. Here, the truncation rank ℓ is used for the least-squares fitting procedure, while a smaller rank $r < \ell$ is employed for the reduced-order DMDc model.

The truncated SVD of the stacked matrix is written as

$$\mathbf{Z} \approx \hat{\mathbf{U}}_\ell \hat{\mathbf{D}}_\ell \hat{\mathbf{V}}_\ell^\top, \quad (2.30)$$

which yields the approximation

$$\mathbf{G} \approx \hat{\mathbf{G}} = \mathbf{Y} \hat{\mathbf{V}}_\ell \hat{\mathbf{D}}_\ell^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{U}}_\ell^\top. \quad (2.31)$$

The operators \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} are recovered by partitioning the left singular vectors according to the state and control dimensions,

$$\hat{\mathbf{U}}_\ell = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{U}}_{l,x} \\ \hat{\mathbf{U}}_{l,u} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{U}}_{l,x} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times \ell}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{U}}_{l,u} \in \mathbb{R}^{c \times \ell}, \quad (2.32)$$

leading to the approximations

$$\hat{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{Y} \hat{\mathbf{V}}_\ell \hat{\mathbf{D}}_\ell^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{U}}_{l,x}^\top, \quad \hat{\mathbf{B}} = \mathbf{Y} \hat{\mathbf{V}}_\ell \hat{\mathbf{D}}_\ell^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{U}}_{l,u}^\top. \quad (2.33)$$

To obtain a reduced-order representation, the output snapshot matrix is projected onto its leading r left singular vectors, $\mathbf{Y} \approx \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_r \tilde{\mathbf{D}}_r \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{r,t}^\top$, where $\tilde{\mathbf{U}}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times r}$ spans the reduced DMDc state space. The reduced operators are then defined as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_r^\top \hat{\mathbf{A}} \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_r, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{B}} = \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_r^\top \hat{\mathbf{B}}, \quad (2.34)$$

with $\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{B}} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times c}$.

The eigen-decomposition of the reduced operator is given by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \mathbf{S} = \mathbf{S} \mathbf{\Lambda}, \quad (2.35)$$

where $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$ contains the eigenvectors of the reduced DMDc operator and $\mathbf{\Lambda}$ is the diagonal matrix of eigenvalues. The corresponding DMDc modes of the full system are computed as

$$\Phi = \mathbf{Y} \hat{\mathbf{V}}_\ell \hat{\mathbf{D}}_\ell^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{U}}_{l,x}^\top \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_r \mathbf{S}. \quad (2.36)$$

The complete DMDc procedure is summarized in Algorithm 3.

Algorithm 3: DMDc via Augmented SVD, taken from Proctor et al. [19]

Input : State snapshots $\mathbf{X}' = [\mathbf{x}_0, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{n-2}]$, $\mathbf{Y} = [\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{n-1}]$, control snapshots $\mathbf{\Upsilon} = [\mathbf{u}_0, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{n-2}]$, fitting rank ℓ and reduced-order rank r

Output: Reduced operators $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}, \tilde{\mathbf{B}}$ and DMDc modes Φ

1. Augment snapshots:

Form the stacked data matrix $\mathbf{Z} \leftarrow \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}' \\ \mathbf{\Upsilon} \end{bmatrix}$.

2. SVD of augmented data (fitting space):

Compute truncated SVD $\mathbf{Z} \approx \hat{\mathbf{U}}_\ell \hat{\mathbf{D}}_\ell \hat{\mathbf{V}}_\ell^\top$. Partition $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_\ell = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{U}}_{l,x} \\ \hat{\mathbf{U}}_{l,u} \end{bmatrix}$, with $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_{l,x} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times \ell}$ and

$$\hat{\mathbf{U}}_{l,u} \in \mathbb{R}^{c \times \ell}.$$

3. SVD of output space (reduced basis):

Compute truncated SVD $\mathbf{Y} \approx \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_r \tilde{\mathbf{D}}_r \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_r^\top$.

4. Approximate reduced operators:

Compute

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \leftarrow \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_r^\top \mathbf{Y} \hat{\mathbf{V}}_\ell \hat{\mathbf{D}}_\ell^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{U}}_{l,x}^\top \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_r, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{B}} \leftarrow \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_r^\top \mathbf{Y} \hat{\mathbf{V}}_\ell \hat{\mathbf{D}}_\ell^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{U}}_{l,u}^\top.$$

5. Eigen-decomposition of reduced operator:

Compute $\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \mathbf{S} = \mathbf{S} \Lambda$.

6. Compute DMDc modes:

$$\Phi \leftarrow \mathbf{Y} \hat{\mathbf{V}}_\ell \hat{\mathbf{D}}_\ell^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{U}}_{l,x}^\top \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_r \mathbf{S}.$$

2.2.3. Time-delayed embedding

Standard DMD and DMDc assume a linear Markovian evolution, where the next state depends only on the immediately preceding one, as seen in Eq. 2.20 and Eq. 2.24. For nonlinear systems such as fluid flows, this first-order dependence is often insufficient to capture the full dynamics.

A common extension is to introduce a *time delay* of length $q \in \mathbb{N}$, meaning that the model uses the past q states to predict the next one. The dynamics are then represented as a higher-order linear recurrence:

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} \approx \mathbf{A}_0 \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{A}_1 \mathbf{x}_{k-1} + \dots + \mathbf{A}_{q-1} \mathbf{x}_{k-q+1}, \quad (2.37)$$

where \mathbf{x}_k is the system state at time-step k and each $\mathbf{A}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ is a linear operator capturing the state contribution from delay i .

This idea follows the principle of Hankel DMD, in which delayed snapshots are stacked to construct an augmented state. This implicitly incorporates multi-step dynamics and yields a model capable of capturing nonlinear flow behaviour more effectively [18].

In this work, the Higher-Order DMD (HODMD) method as proposed by Clainche and Vega [14] is

used. Although originally formulated for standard DMD, it is extended here to DMDc by applying the same delay-embedding procedure to the control inputs. The procedure consists of the following steps:

Step 1: Dimension reduction

A truncated SVD of rank r is applied to \mathbf{X} ,

$$\mathbf{X} \approx \mathbf{U}_r \mathbf{D}_r \mathbf{V}_r^T, \quad (2.38)$$

yielding the reduced snapshot matrix

$$\widehat{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{U}_r^T \mathbf{X}, \quad \widehat{\mathbf{X}} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times n}. \quad (2.39)$$

Step 2: Construct delay-embedded matrices

Using the delays q , the reduced snapshots are augmented as:

$$\widehat{\mathbf{X}}'_q = \begin{bmatrix} \widehat{\mathbf{x}}_0 & \widehat{\mathbf{x}}_1 & \cdots & \widehat{\mathbf{x}}_{n-q-2} \\ \widehat{\mathbf{x}}_1 & \widehat{\mathbf{x}}_2 & \cdots & \widehat{\mathbf{x}}_{n-q-1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \widehat{\mathbf{x}}_{q-1} & \widehat{\mathbf{x}}_q & \cdots & \widehat{\mathbf{x}}_{n-2} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \widehat{\mathbf{Y}}_q = \begin{bmatrix} \widehat{\mathbf{x}}_1 & \widehat{\mathbf{x}}_2 & \cdots & \widehat{\mathbf{x}}_{n-q-1} \\ \widehat{\mathbf{x}}_2 & \widehat{\mathbf{x}}_3 & \cdots & \widehat{\mathbf{x}}_{n-q} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \widehat{\mathbf{x}}_q & \widehat{\mathbf{x}}_{q+1} & \cdots & \widehat{\mathbf{x}}_{n-1} \end{bmatrix},$$

with

$$\widehat{\mathbf{X}}'_q, \widehat{\mathbf{Y}}_q \in \mathbb{R}^{(r \cdot q) \times (n-q-1)}.$$

The control inputs are delay-embedded in the same fashion:

$$\widehat{\mathbf{Y}}_q = \begin{bmatrix} \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_0 & \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_1 & \cdots & \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_{n-q-2} \\ \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_1 & \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_2 & \cdots & \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_{n-q-1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_{q-1} & \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_q & \cdots & \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_{n-2} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \widehat{\mathbf{Y}}_q \in \mathbb{R}^{(q \cdot p) \times (n-q-1)}.$$

Step 3: Compute delay-embedded DMDc operators

The delay-embedded DMDc operators are obtained by solving

$$\widehat{\mathbf{Y}}_q = \widehat{\mathbf{A}} \widehat{\mathbf{X}}'_q + \widehat{\mathbf{B}} \widehat{\mathbf{\Upsilon}}_q, \quad (2.40)$$

using standard DMDc as given in Algorithm 3.

The operator dimensions in are,

$$\widehat{\mathbf{A}} \in \mathbb{R}^{(r \cdot q) \times (r \cdot q)}, \quad \widehat{\mathbf{B}} \in \mathbb{R}^{(r \cdot q) \times (q \cdot c)}.$$

This yields a DMDc model with q delays in state and actuation inputs.

2.2.4. DMDc formulation with time-delayed embedding

This section presents a more general formulation of DMDc with time-delayed embedding and general truncation ranks, and describes the methodology for rolling out the state vector from a given initial condition to generate predictions.

Let $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ denote the snapshot matrix obtained from the simulation, where m is the number of spatial degrees of freedom and n is the number of time snapshots. To reduce the dimensionality of the data, a truncated SVD of rank η is applied,

$$\mathbf{X} \approx \mathbf{U}_\eta \mathbf{D}_\eta \mathbf{V}_\eta^\top, \quad (2.41)$$

where $\mathbf{U}_\eta \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times \eta}$ contains the leading POD modes. Projection onto this basis yields the reduced snapshot matrix

$$\widehat{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{U}_\eta^\top \mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{\eta \times n}. \quad (2.42)$$

Each row of $\widehat{\mathbf{X}}$ represents the temporal evolution of a single modal coefficient. This space is referred to as the *reduced-snapshot subspace*.

To improve robustness and capture higher-order temporal correlations, a q -step time-delay embedding (see Sec. 2.2.3) is applied to the reduced snapshot matrix. The resulting delay-embedded state matrix is

$$\widehat{\mathbf{X}}_q \in \mathbb{R}^{(\eta \cdot q) \times (n - q)}. \quad (2.43)$$

The control signal

$$\mathbf{\Upsilon} \in \mathbb{R}^{c \times n}$$

is delay-embedded in the same manner, yielding

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}}_q \in \mathbb{R}^{(c \cdot q) \times (n - q - 1)}. \quad (2.44)$$

These delay-embedded matrices form the inputs used to fit the DMDc model.

During the model-fitting step, a second truncation is applied to the delay-embedded data in order to obtain a reduced-order representation called the *delay-embedded* subspace. The truncation rank for the DMDc model fitting is denoted by κ . In practice, the *PyDMD* library [3] is used for the fitting, and the resulting reduced operators satisfy

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \mathbb{R}^{\kappa \times \kappa}, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{B}} \in \mathbb{R}^{\kappa \times (c \cdot q)}. \quad (2.45)$$

In *PyDMD*, the reduced basis for the delay-embedded subspace is obtained from an SVD of the one-step time-shifted matrix

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}} = \hat{\mathbf{X}}_q[:, 1:\text{end}], \quad (2.46)$$

where zero-based indexing is assumed. The factorization

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}} \approx \hat{\mathbf{U}}_\kappa \hat{\mathbf{D}}_\kappa \hat{\mathbf{V}}_\kappa^T \quad (2.47)$$

with

$$\hat{\mathbf{U}}_\kappa \in \mathbb{R}^{(\eta \cdot q) \times \kappa},$$

provides the basis for the reduced *delay-embedded* subspace.

Prediction in reduced space. Let $\mathbf{x}_{0,q} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times q}$ denote the initial sequence of q states, Projection onto the common reduced basis yields the initial reduced state,

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{0,q} = \mathbf{U}_\eta^T \mathbf{x}_{0,q} \in \mathbb{R}^{\eta \times q}.$$

which are stacked into a single vector $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{\eta \cdot q \times 1}$. The corresponding initial condition in the reduced delay-embedded space is obtained via

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0 = \hat{\mathbf{U}}_\kappa^T \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^\kappa. \quad (2.48)$$

Predictions are performed for a new control-input sequence

$$[\mathbf{u}_0, \mathbf{u}_1, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{n-2}], \quad \mathbf{u}_k \in \mathbb{R}^c,$$

which must be delay-embedded prior to application $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{c \cdot q}$. The reduced state evolves according to

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k + \tilde{\mathbf{B}} \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k, \quad k = 0, \dots, n-2. \quad (2.49)$$

Stacking all predicted reduced states yields $\tilde{\mathbf{X}}_{\text{pred}} \in \mathbb{R}^{\kappa \times n}$.

Reconstruction. The predicted reduced states are first lifted back to the delay-embedded space,

$$\hat{\mathbf{X}}_{\text{pred},q} = \hat{\mathbf{U}}_{\kappa} \tilde{\mathbf{X}}_{\text{pred}} \in \mathbb{R}^{(\eta \cdot q) \times n}. \quad (2.50)$$

The modal coefficients in the reduced-snapshot subspace are then obtained by extracting the final block of η rows,

$$\hat{\mathbf{X}}_{\text{pred}} = \hat{\mathbf{X}}_{\text{pred},q}[-\eta:\text{end}, :] \in \mathbb{R}^{\eta \times n}. \quad (2.51)$$

Finally, the full-state prediction is recovered by lifting the modal coefficients back to the original state space,

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{pred}} = \mathbf{U}_{\eta} \hat{\mathbf{X}}_{\text{pred}} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}. \quad (2.52)$$

2.2.5. Multi-Operator Random Shuffling

The Multi-Operator Random Shuffling (MORS) framework combines multiple DMDc models to improve predictive robustness. Rather than relying on a single identified operator, predictions are generated by switching between several DMDc models during the rollout. By doing so, the systematic bias associated with any individual model can be mitigated.

To this end, a *library* of DMDc models is constructed, where each model is trained on snapshot data corresponding to a distinct actuation signal. In order to allow seamless switching between models during prediction, all operators are expressed in a *common reduced coordinate system*. This is achieved by constructing a common reduced basis from the snapshot data of all signals in the library.

Let S denote the number of available datasets, each associated with a distinct actuation signal. For $i = 1, \dots, S$, let $\mathbf{X}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ denote the snapshot matrix containing n snapshots of an m -dimensional flow state. A joint snapshot matrix is formed by concatenating all datasets along the temporal dimension,

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{joint}} = [\mathbf{X}_1, \mathbf{X}_2, \dots, \mathbf{X}_S] \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times (S \cdot n)},$$

where it is assumed that each dataset contains the same number of snapshots.

A POD basis is extracted from the joint snapshot matrix via the SVD

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{joint}} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{V}^T,$$

and truncated to rank r , yielding the common reduced basis

$$\mathbf{u}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times r}.$$

The matrix \mathbf{u}_r defines the *common reduced basis* shared by all models in the library.

Each snapshot dataset is then projected onto this common basis,

$$\hat{\mathbf{X}}_i = \mathbf{u}_r^T \mathbf{X}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times n}.$$

Once the common basis is fixed, the identification of each DMDc model proceeds exactly as described in Sec. 2.2.4, i.e., time-delay embedding with q delays is applied, followed by model fitting.

This procedure yields, for each dataset $j = 1, \dots, S$, a triplet

$$(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{(j)}, \tilde{\mathbf{B}}^{(j)}, \hat{\mathbf{U}}_r^{(j)}),$$

where the pair $(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{(j)}, \tilde{\mathbf{B}}^{(j)})$ constitutes the reduced DMDc *operator* associated with the j -th dataset, and $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_r^{(j)}$ denotes the truncated basis of the time-delay-embedded state matrix obtained during the corresponding DMDc fitting procedure. A separate time-delay basis is retained for each model, since it is learned independently from the corresponding training data. Although different truncation ranks could be chosen for different datasets, a common rank r is adopted here for brevity.

Prediction with Random Model Switching. During prediction, the system state evolves in the common reduced space defined by \mathbf{u}_r . Since time-delay embedding is employed, the initial condition must include the required delay history. Let $\mathbf{x}_{0,q} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times q}$ denote the initial sequence of q states. Projection onto the common reduced basis yields the initial reduced state,

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{0,q} = \mathbf{u}_r^T \mathbf{x}_{0,q} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times q},$$

which are stacked into a single vector $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{r \cdot q \times 1}$.

At each prediction step k , a *model-selection function* $\sigma(k) \in \{1, \dots, S\}$ selects one of the available DMDc models from the library. The value of $\sigma(k)$ is a scalar index identifying which reduced DMDc operator $(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{(i)}, \tilde{\mathbf{B}}^{(i)})$ is used at time step k .

Model-Shuffling Strategy. Rather than switching models at every time step, the selected model is held constant for a block of n_{shuf} consecutive prediction steps, where n_{shuf} represents the shuffling rate. After each block, a new model index is randomly drawn from the set $\{1, \dots, S\}$. The evolution of the model-selection function is defined as

$$\sigma(k) = \begin{cases} \sigma(k-1), & k \bmod n_{\text{shuf}} \neq 0, \\ i \sim \text{Uniform}\{1, \dots, S\}, & k \bmod n_{\text{shuf}} = 0, \end{cases}$$

where $\text{Uniform}\{1, \dots, S\}$ denotes the discrete uniform distribution over the model indices, and $\sigma(0)$ is drawn once at the start. This stochastic selection mechanism defines the Multi-Operator Random Shuffling (MORS) predictor.

Let $i = \sigma(k)$ denote the selected model at prediction step k . The state is first projected into the model-specific reduced space,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k = \hat{\mathbf{U}}_r^{(i)\top} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k.$$

The dynamics are then advanced under the delay-embedded control input $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k$,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{(i)} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k + \tilde{\mathbf{B}}^{(i)} \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k.$$

Finally, the updated state is mapped back to the common reduced space,

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1} = \hat{\mathbf{U}}_r^{(i)} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}.$$

Repeating this process over the control sequence $\{\mathbf{u}_k\}_{k=0}^{n-2}$ produces the reduced prediction matrix

$$\hat{\mathbf{X}}_{\text{pred}} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 & \hat{\mathbf{x}}_1 & \dots & \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{n-1} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times n}.$$

The final prediction in the full state space is obtained by

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{pred}} = \mathbf{U}_r \hat{\mathbf{X}}_{\text{pred}}[-r:\text{end},:],$$

where the slice extracts the final block corresponding to the current prediction, excluding the delay history. This *random shuffling* strategy yields the Multi-Operator Random Shuffling (MORS) predictor, which randomly selects operators at each prediction step. The implementation is summarized in Algorithm. 4.

Algorithm 4: MORS: Multi-Operator Random Shuffling

Input : Library snapshots $\{\mathbf{X}^{(j)}\}_{j=1}^S$ and controls $\{\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}^{(j)}\}_{j=1}^S$;
 Delayed initial state $\mathbf{x}_{0,q}$ and target controls $\{\mathbf{u}_k\}_{k=0}^{n-2}$;
 Rank r , delay q , and shuffling interval n_{shuf}

Output: Predicted snapshots \mathbf{X}_{pred}

1. Common basis construction:

Form the joint snapshot matrix $\mathbf{X}_{\text{joint}} = [\mathbf{X}^{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{X}^{(S)}]$.

Compute its SVD $\mathbf{X}_{\text{joint}} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{V}^T$ and retain the truncated common basis $\mathbf{U}_r = \mathbf{U}(:, :r)$.

2. Library model identification:

for $j = 1, \dots, S$ **do**

Project snapshots onto the common basis: $\hat{\mathbf{X}}_q^{(j)} = \mathbf{U}_r^T \mathbf{X}^{(j)}$.

Apply time-delay embedding to obtain $(\hat{\mathbf{X}}_q^{(j)}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}}_q^{(j)})$.

Fit a DMDC model to $(\hat{\mathbf{X}}_q^{(j)}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}}_q^{(j)})$, yielding $(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{(j)}, \tilde{\mathbf{B}}^{(j)}, \hat{\mathbf{U}}_r^{(j)})$.

end

3. Target initialization in common space:

Take q initial snapshots $\mathbf{x}_{0,q} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times q}$.

Project to the common reduced space: $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{0,q} = \mathbf{U}_r^T \mathbf{x}_{0,q} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times q}$.

Stack to form vector: $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{r \cdot q \times 1}$.

4. Random shuffling rollout:

Delay-embed the target control sequence to obtain $\{\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k\}_{k=0}^{n-2}$.

Draw an initial model index $i \sim \text{Uniform}\{1, \dots, S\}$.

for $k = 0, \dots, n - 2$ **do**

if $k > 0$ **and** $k \bmod n_{\text{shuf}} = 0$ **then**

Draw a new model index $i \sim \text{Uniform}\{1, \dots, S\}$.

end

Project into the model-specific space: $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k = \hat{\mathbf{U}}_r^{(i)T} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k$.

Advance one step:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{(i)} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k + \tilde{\mathbf{B}}^{(i)} \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k.$$

Lift back to the common space:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1} = \hat{\mathbf{U}}_r^{(i)} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1}.$$

end

5. Reconstruction to physical space:

Form the reduced prediction matrix $\hat{\mathbf{X}}_{\text{pred}} = [\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{n-1}]$.

Recover the full-state prediction:

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{pred}} = \mathbf{U}_r \hat{\mathbf{X}}_{\text{pred}}[-r:\text{end}, :].$$

3. Numerical Method

The following section outlines the numerical setup used in this thesis. As this work builds on the studies in [7, 24], the overall flow control problem remains the same as the previous work. The detailed summary of the numerical setup can be found in [24]. Some adjustments to the setup were made, as detailed in [7], and the same adjusted setup is used in this work. The set-up is briefly described here.

3.1. Flow past a cylinder

The flow problem used to investigate active flow control using DRL is the two-dimensional flow past a cylinder in a rectangular channel. This configuration is widely used for benchmarking and validating numerical schemes, as well as for investigating reduced-order modeling methodologies. A major advantage of this setup is its relatively low computational cost, which provides the flexibility needed to perform various experiments.

3.1.1. Numerical set-up

The two-dimensional test case considered in this work corresponds to an incompressible flow past a circular cylinder at a Reynolds number $Re = 100$. The geometry of the computational domain is shown in Fig. 3.3. The configuration represents a rectangular channel with a cylinder placed off-center. The kinematic viscosity is set to $\nu = 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, and the inlet velocity is then chosen as $u_{\text{inlet}} = 1 \text{ m/s}$ to satisfy

$$Re = \frac{u_{\text{inlet}} d}{\nu} = 100,$$

for cylinder diameter $d = 0.1 \text{ m}$.

The inlet boundary condition follows a parabolic velocity profile,

$$\mathbf{u}^*(x^* = 0, y^*) = \frac{4U_m y(h - y)}{h^2},$$

where $U_m = 1.5 u_{\text{inlet}}$ is the centerline velocity and h is the channel height. A no-slip condition is imposed along the top and bottom boundaries, while at the outlet, a zero-gradient condition is applied for the velocity, and a fixed reference pressure is prescribed. The angular velocity of the cylinder is prescribed by fixing the velocity at the cylinder wall according to

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \boldsymbol{\omega}(t) \times (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_c),$$

where $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ denotes the velocity at position \mathbf{x} and time t , \mathbf{x}_c is the center of the cylinder, and $\boldsymbol{\omega}(t)$ is the angular velocity vector. For the two-dimensional configuration considered in this work, the rotation axis is normal to the flow plane, such that $\boldsymbol{\omega}(t) = \omega(t) \mathbf{e}_z$, where \mathbf{e}_z is the unit vector in the out-of-plane direction.

The boundary conditions are schematically shown in Fig. 3.1.

Figure 3.1.: Boundary conditions. Here $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_c$ denotes the position vector measured from the center of the cylinder. The image is taken from [24] and then edited.

The computational mesh shown in Fig. 3.2 is generated using the *blockMesh* utility of OpenFOAM and contains approximately 21,250 cells. The resolution is chosen based on the grid independence study done in the previous work [7,24]. The flow can be described using the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations given in Sec. A.1 and are solved using a pressure-velocity coupling scheme with *pimpleFOAM* solver on *OpenFOAM*.

Figure 3.2.: Computational mesh.

All times reported in this work are expressed in convective time units (CTU). The convective time scale in this flow problem is defined as

$$t_{\text{conv}} = \frac{d}{u_{\text{inlet}}} = 0.1 \text{ s},$$

And time in CTU is $\tilde{t} = t/t_{\text{conv}}$. The flow field is initialized to zero at $\tilde{t} = 0$, and reaches a quasi-steady state at $\tilde{t} = 40$. Therefore, in most of the applications, like training the optimal policy using DRL or fitting the DMDc model, the system is allowed to evolve without actuation until it reaches

the quasi-steady state. The DRL training process requires state measurements, which are used as input to the flow controller. This is provided as pressure values at 12 probes at the locations shown in Fig. 3.3. The actuation used to control the flow is the angular velocity of the cylinder, with bounds

Figure 3.3.: Geometry of numerical domain, where the crosses denote the location of sensors. d is the cylinder diameter. The image is taken from [29].

$\omega(t) \in [-5, 5]$ rad/s as suggested in [7].

Control problem

The objective function for the active flow control problem, which is termed as the reward function, is to maximize

$$R_t = 3 - (c_{d,t} + 0.1 |c_{l,t}|), \quad (3.1)$$

where $c_{d,t}$ and $c_{l,t}$ denote the instantaneous drag and lift coefficients acting on the cylinder at time t , respectively. The objective is to minimize the drag coefficient while simultaneously reducing fluctuations in the lift coefficient.

3.2. Software and Computational resources

This section gives an overview of the computing resources used for the simulations. A brief account is also provided of the libraries and applications used to conduct the required simulations.

Barnard HPC

To run the more computationally expensive jobs, the HPC cluster "Barnard" at TU Dresden ¹ is used. The HPC is mainly used to run *Partitioned SVD* algorithm for the turbulent flow past a cylinder in a 3D case (see Sec. 4.3.2). All remaining simulations are performed on a local machine equipped with Intel® Core™ i7-11800H CPU (8 cores) and 16 GB of RAM.

OpenFOAM

OpenFOAM is an open-source CFD software package capable of solving a wide range of fluid-mechanical problems [6]. In this work, OpenFOAM v2406 is used as the solver for running the CFD simulations of flow past a cylinder, as discussed in Sec. 3.1 and Sec. 4.3.2.

PyDMD

PyDMD is a Python package for Dynamic Mode Decomposition and its various extensions [4,8]. It automates many of the computational and post-processing steps involved in DMD workflows, making it an ideal choice for constructing the reduced-order models used in this work.

Drlfoam

drlfoam [17] is a Python framework that implements the deep reinforcement learning–OpenFOAM coupling loop, enabling the training of flow-control policies with OpenFOAM as the environment. In this work, the *drlfoam* framework is extended by replacing only the environment component and introducing a reduced-order model in its place.

¹HPC cluster at TU Dresden: <https://tu-dresden.de/zih/hochleistungsrechnen/hpc>

4. Partitioned singular value decomposition

This section presents the implementation and validation of the partitioned SVD algorithm. A key part of the project is the construction of a reduced-order model for the flow using Dynamic Mode Decomposition with Control. Computing the operators of the DMDC model requires evaluating the SVD of the snapshot matrix. However, for large and complex datasets, the SVD computation becomes a major bottleneck due to its significant memory requirements.

Partitioned SVD provides an effective way to alleviate this issue. Previous work by Maric et al. [13] implements the partitioned SVD algorithm that partitions the snapshot matrix only in the spatial direction. In the present work, this approach is extended to allow partitioning in both space and time. Moreover, the method is implemented to run in an online fashion, where the SVD is updated in batches of data as the simulation runs. This approach greatly reduces the need for hard-disk storage, because the snapshot data does not have to be saved permanently. Each batch of data is kept in memory only till it is used to update the SVD, after which it is discarded.

Although the online SVD is not strictly essential for the present work, since the flow configuration considered here is relatively inexpensive to simulate, its implementation is included for completeness. More importantly, it provides a foundation for future applications in which the flow is more complex or in which the DMDC model must be continuously updated during training.

4.1. Implementation

The algorithm and theoretical background for the partitioned SVD approach are discussed in Sec. 2.1. The method is implemented in Python using the SmartSim library [10], which provides a framework for managing data produced by simulations and enables the application of ML algorithms to that data. SmartSim facilitates the coupling of CFD solvers, which are mostly written in languages like C++, C, or FORTRAN, to Python-based machine learning workflows. This coupling is achieved through an in-memory database that acts as a central communication hub between the simulation and the ML components.

A typical SmartSim workflow begins by instantiating an *Experiment* object, which serves as the main interface for creating and managing different stages of the workflow. Within this object, all components required for coupling ML and CFD can be created. Executable code like CFD solvers are launched as *Model* instances, created using `Experiment.create_model`, whereas data management components such as the SmartRedis database are instantiated as *Orchestrator* objects using `Experiment.create_database`. In this way, an OpenFOAM simulation can be launched directly from a Python script, with runtime arguments (e.g. number of MPI ranks) configured through the

corresponding *Model* instance. SmartSim also provides support for HPC execution, automatically interfacing with job managers such as *Slurm* and *PBS*, with the same code that can also run on local machines without much modification. *Model* instances support non-blocking execution, allowing the simulation to run in the background while subsequent parts of the Python workflow continue.

OpenFOAM is used as the CFD solver in this work. The OpenFOAM-SmartSim repository [16], developed as part of the work by Maric et al. [13], provide essential functionalities for coupling OpenFOAM simulations with the SmartRedis database. In particular, the `fieldsToSmartRedis` function object writes OpenFOAM fields to the database as *Tensor* objects, the default array datatype used in the *PyTorch* library. In this study, both pressure and velocity fields are written to the database.

Once the field data have been written to the database, the SVD of the snapshot matrix is computed incrementally by processing the data in batches. A batch is a consecutive set of b snapshots, where b is the batch size. For the complete snapshot matrix \mathbf{X} , the j -th batch is denoted as $\mathbf{X}_{(b-1) \cdot j : b \cdot j}$, meaning it contains snapshots from time index $(b-1) \cdot j$ up to $b \cdot j$. Each batch is only processed once the OpenFOAM simulation has advanced sufficiently to produce the corresponding timesteps. To ensure this synchronization, the `poll_list_length()` method from the SmartSim `Client` class is used, it polls the database and pauses execution until all necessary field data for the next batch is available.

Each snapshot is constructed by vertically stacking the pressure and velocity components. For 2D simulations,

$$\mathbf{x}_k = [p, u_x, u_y]^T,$$

and for 3D simulations,

$$\mathbf{x}_k = [p, u_x, u_y, u_z]^T,$$

where p is the flattened pressure field and u_x, u_y, u_z are the flattened velocity components. The fields are non-dimensionalized using reference velocity u_{ref} . The resulting non-dimensional variables are given by

$$\tilde{p} = \frac{p}{u_{\text{ref}}^2}, \quad \tilde{u}_x = \frac{u_x}{u_{\text{ref}}}, \quad \tilde{u}_y = \frac{u_y}{u_{\text{ref}}}, \quad \tilde{u}_z = \frac{u_z}{u_{\text{ref}}}, \quad (4.1)$$

where $\tilde{p}, \tilde{u}_x, \tilde{u}_y,$ and \tilde{u}_z denote the non-dimensional pressure and velocity components.

Thus, the batch size b determines the number of temporal partitions (columns), while the spatial partitioning is naturally obtained from domain decomposition in parallel OpenFOAM runs, where each MPI rank contributes one spatial block (row partition).

For each SVD computation in the algorithm, the decomposition is truncated to a specified rank r . This rank truncation retains only the leading singular values and their corresponding singular vectors. This substantially reduces the computational and memory costs.

An *Ensemble* in the SmartSim library allows the launching of multiple *Model* objects simultaneously, each of which can be parametrized according to requirement. This provides an ideal framework to execute the SVD computation of the individual partitions as required by the partitioned SVD algorithm. Each field block is partitioned independently, so the ensemble is parameterized by both the field name and the number of MPI ranks.

For example, in the 2D cylinder case with fields $[p, u_x, u_y]$ and a domain decomposition of 10 partitions, the ensemble launches 30 *Model* instances, one for each field partition pair. Each model computes the SVD of its assigned partition using the standard NumPy [15] function `numpy.linalg.svd`. A similar ensemble is employed during the reconstruction stage, where the POD modes for each partition are mapped back to the full-field representation.

Using SmartSim *Model* objects for SVD computation provides many advantages. It ensures that the same workflow can transition between local and HPC launches. Moreover, with minor implementation changes, these ensembles can be configured to execute their models concurrently (within memory limits), enabling the SVD computation across multiple partitions to run in parallel and significantly reducing overall runtime.

The implementation of the Partitioned SVD algorithm is available in the GitHub repository [20].

Usage in HPC clusters

SmartSim provides a convenient and flexible way for deploying simulation and machine-learning workflows onto an HPC cluster without requiring many changes to the implementation code. The transition from a local workstation to a cluster environment is achieved simply by changing the *launcher* argument when instantiating the SmartSim *Experiment*. For example,

```
exp = Experiment(name="my_exp", launcher="slurm")
```

switches the execution backend from the default *"local"* launcher to the *"slurm"* launcher used on HPC systems. Once this is done, SmartSim automatically switches from running tasks on the local workstation to submitting and managing jobs on the HPC cluster by generating the appropriate Slurm batch scripts, allocating user-defined compute resources (CPUs, GPUs, memory), and submitting the jobs to the cluster's scheduling system. This abstraction hides much of the complexity normally associated with batch-based HPC execution and allows the same code to run on compute nodes easily.

Deploying a SmartRedis database (Orchestrator) on the cluster follows a similar workflow. When the database is created in batch mode, SmartSim constructs a Slurm job script and submits it to the scheduler such that The database is launched on the allocated cluster nodes. For example, a database with three nodes can be created using,

```
db_cluster = exp.create_database(db_nodes=3, db_port=6780,
    batch=True, time="00:10:00", interface="ib0"
)
```

Here, choosing an appropriate network interface is important. Local systems usually use the loop-back interface `"lo"` for communication between processes on the same machine; however, this interface cannot be used across multiple nodes. On the TU Dresden HPC cluster, the InfiniBand interface `"ib0"` provides high-bandwidth, low-latency inter-node communication, making it well suited for communication between the database and the driver script, both of which usually lie in the HPC compute nodes. Resource allocation for the Redis database in HPC requires one additional step. In batch mode, memory and CPU requests must be set through slurm arguments attached directly to the Orchestrator object. This is achieved using the `set_batch_arg` method, which inputs resource specifications into the generated job script. For example, additional CPU cores can be allocated using

```
db_cluster.set_batch_arg("cpus-per-task", "104")
```

This is particularly important when working with large, memory-intensive datasets, where insufficient memory may lead to out-of-memory failures either in SmartRedis or in the simulation workflow.

SmartRedis data storage and naming scheme

Snapshots written by OpenFOAM are stored in the SmartRedis database using a specific naming structure that identifies each tensor based on the field name, MPI rank, and time index. Each entry is composed of two components, namely a `field` label and a `dataset` label. The templates used are

```
field      "field_name_{name}_patch_{patch}";
dataset    "{fo_name}_time_index_{time_index}_mpi_rank_{mpi_rank}";
```

Here, `field_name` corresponds to the OpenFOAM variable being written (e.g. p , U), and `mpi_rank` identifies the spatial sub-partition. Each tensor represents the domain decomposed portion of the full flow field on a specific MPI rank.

The entry `patch` specifies which OpenFOAM patch the data originates from. Typically, this is the *internal* data, which is used to create the snapshot matrix. Others include the boundary patches such as *inlet*, *outlet*, or *walls*. The boundary data is ignored when building the snapshot matrix.

The variable `fo_name` corresponds to the name of the *fieldsToSmartRedis* function object, specified in the *controlDict* file in OpenFOAM. This ensures that data written by different function objects can also be determined. Therefore, a specific field of data can be identified uniquely and then extracted using the combined key of the form `dataset.field`, which provides access to the desired field component at a specific time and rank. Here, the `time_index` represents the temporal position based on the solver time step Δt_{solver} . However, data are only written to the SmartRedis database at intervals of Δt_{write} , which means tensors are not stored at every possible `time_index`. The indices at which snapshots are available can therefore be determined from the ratio between the write interval and the solver time step. A snapshot is written every

$$s_{\text{snap}} = \frac{\Delta t_{\text{write}}}{\Delta t_{\text{solver}}}$$

solver iterations, where s_{snap} denotes the *snapshot stride*. Consequently, the k -th stored snapshot can be queried from the database with

$$\text{time_index} = s_{\text{snap}} \cdot k.$$

4.2. Reconstruction

The rank- r truncated POD approximation of the snapshot matrix provides a low-dimensional representation of the flow field that retains the dominant coherent structures. By storing only the leading r modes, the essential flow dynamics can be captured using only a fraction of the memory required to store the full snapshot matrix. The rank- r reconstruction of the snapshot matrix can be computed based on truncated SVD. The reconstructed snapshot matrix can be written back into the OpenFOAM field files using the *svdToFoam* utility, developed as part of the work by Maric et al. [13]. Implementation and installation details are available in the *openfoam-smartsim* repository [16].

This capability is useful for two main reasons. First, it allows visualization and inspection of the dominant POD modes directly within OpenFOAM, providing physical insight into the flow structures captured by the truncated POD modes. Second, once the reconstructed fields are written into the OpenFOAM format, standard post-processing utilities such as *forceCoefficients* can be applied to compute lift and drag forces. This provides a workflow for converting NumPy arrays or tensor data from different flow fields, such as pressure or velocity, into OpenFOAM fields. This is an integral part of the present work, as shown in the later sections, where flow fields predicted by the reduced-order model (DMDc) are converted to the OpenFOAM format to evaluate the forces acting on them.

4.2.1. svdToFoam

The *svdToFoam* utility, originally developed in the *openfoam-smartsim* repository [16], is used to convert SVD-based reconstructions from the SmartRedis database to OpenFOAM field format. In the repository, the utility was implemented to handle only the velocity field data. For the present work, *svdToFoam* is extended to support velocity and scalar fields, allowing it to reconstruct not only the velocity field but also pressure p and other scalar quantities. The updated implementation of `svdToFoam.C` is available in the project repository [20].

The executable is configured via command-line options that specify (i) the name of the field to be reconstructed (`-fieldName`), (ii) the SVD rank used for the reconstruction (`-svdRank`), and (iii) the name of the SmartRedis function object that wrote the data (`-FOName`). A typical usage would be:

```
svdToFoam -case <caseDir> -fieldName p
          -svdRank 40 -FOName dataToSmartRedis
```

Internally, these parameters, along with the MPI rank and `time_index`, are used to identify the tensor key needed to fetch the data. Each reconstruction tensor is expected to follow the naming pattern,

```
rec_ensemble_r<svdRank>_field_name_<fieldName>_<mpiRank>
.rank_<svdRank>_field_name_<fieldName>_mpi_rank_<mpiRank>_time_index_<index>
```

where `<svdRank>` is the SVD truncation rank, `<fieldName>` is the name of the reconstructed field (e.g. U , p), `<mpiRank>` is the MPI rank identifier, and `<index>` corresponds to the OpenFOAM time index consistent with the snapshot stride. This naming pattern is important, as *svdToFoam* uses it to determine which tensor to fetch at each output time.

For every output time, a field tensor is retrieved from the database and mapped either to a *volVectorField* (for U) or to a *volScalarField* (for scalar fields such as p).

To ensure consistency with the OpenFOAM case setup, each reconstructed field is initialised using a template field, read from the `0` directory. The reconstructed data is then assigned to the internal field, after which the boundary conditions are enforced using `correctBoundaryConditions()`. This OpenFOAM function applies the boundary specifications as defined in the `0.org` file of the case. The core reconstruction logic for a scalar field is shown in Listing. 4.1. The reconstruction for a vector field is done using a similar logic as shown in the Listing. 4.2.

A similar implementation is used to write the fields corresponding to the major global modes in an OpenFOAM-readable format, where each mode is obtained from the left singular vectors. The extended version of *svdToFoam* developed in this work provides a simple way to convert reconstructed NumPy arrays or tensors into OpenFOAM field files and automatically enforces the correct

```

volScalarField scalar
(
    IOobject(fieldName, runTime.timeName(), mesh,
              IOobject::NO_READ, IOobject::AUTO_WRITE),
    scalarTemplate // boundary conditions from 0/fieldName
);

// Fetch tensor from SmartRedis
client.get_tensor(tensorName, reconstruction, dims, type, SRMemLayoutNested);

// Assign values
forAll (scalar.internalFieldRef(), cellI)
{
    scalar.internalFieldRef()[cellI] = ((double*)reconstruction)[cellI];
}

scalar.correctBoundaryConditions();
scalar.write();

```

Listing 4.1: OpenFOAM C++ snippet assigning a `volScalarField` from a SmartRedis tensor.

```

volVectorField U
(
    IOobject("U", runTime.timeName(), mesh,
              IOobject::NO_READ, IOobject::AUTO_WRITE),
    Utemplate
);

// Fetch tensor from SmartRedis
client.get_tensor(tensorName, reconstruction, dims, type, SRMemLayoutNested);

// Assign values
forAll (U.internalFieldRef(), cellI)
{
    vector Ui
    (
        ((double**)reconstruction)[cellI][0],
        ((double**)reconstruction)[cellI][1],
        ((double**)reconstruction)[cellI][2]
    );
    U.internalFieldRef()[cellI] = Ui;
}

U.correctBoundaryConditions();
U.write();

```

Listing 4.2: OpenFOAM C++ snippet assigning a `volVectorField U` from a SmartRedis tensor.

boundary conditions. This functionality is an essential component of the workflow used for later tasks in the thesis.

4.2.2. Force coefficient evaluation

Once the reconstructed NumPy arrays are written back into OpenFOAM fields using *svdToFoam*, desired post-processing can be done on these fields using OpenFOAM utilities. In this work, the lift and drag force coefficients are of particular interest. These can be evaluated using the standard OpenFOAM post-processing utility *forceCoeffs*. To do this, a dedicated OpenFOAM dictionary is created (here named `FO_force`), in which the patches of interest, reference values, and output settings for the force coefficients are specified. One such dictionary that is used in this work is shown in Listing A.1 for representative purposes.

This dictionary is placed in the system directory (e.g., as `system/FO_force`), then the force coefficients can be computed by running

```
pimpleFoam -postProcess -dict system/FO_force
```

Here *pimpleFoam* is only an example solver and is replaced for the other cases accordingly.

4.3. Test Cases

The partitioned SVD algorithm is tested on two flow configurations to check the validity of the code, namely: (i) flow past a circular cylinder in 2D, and (ii) turbulent flow past a cylinder in 3D.

Validation approach

To validate the partitioned SVD algorithm, its results are compared against a direct SVD performed on the full snapshot matrix using the standard `numpy.linalg.svd`. This reference approach is hereafter referred to as the *direct SVD*.

For a snapshot matrix \mathbf{X} , the rank- r truncated reconstruction obtained with the direct SVD is given by

$$\mathbf{X}_D = \mathbf{U}_r \mathbf{D}_r \mathbf{V}_r^T, \quad (4.2)$$

where \mathbf{U}_r , \mathbf{D}_r , and \mathbf{V}_r denote the truncated POD modes obtained from the direct SVD.

Similarly, the reconstruction obtained using the partitioned approach is denoted by \mathbf{X}_P and is given by

$$\mathbf{X}_P = \bar{\mathbf{U}}_r \bar{\mathbf{D}}_r \bar{\mathbf{V}}_r^T, \quad (4.3)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{U}}_r$, $\bar{\mathbf{D}}_r$, and $\bar{\mathbf{V}}_r$ are the POD modes computed using the *partitioned SVD*.

The two reconstructions are compared using the relative reconstruction error

$$\varepsilon_{\text{rec}} = \frac{\|\mathbf{X}_P - \mathbf{X}_D\|_2}{\|\mathbf{X}_D\|_2}. \quad (4.4)$$

This provides a quantitative measure of the accuracy of the partitioned SVD code. After reconstruction, the fields obtained from the partitioned SVD method are written back into OpenFOAM format using the *svdToFoam* utility. Lift and drag coefficients are then evaluated using the *forceCoeffs* function object (see Sec. 4.2.2). This allows direct comparison between forces computed using the full-order fields and the reconstructed ones.

Input parameters

The partitioned SVD algorithm requires many input parameters that define how the snapshots are generated, stored, and partitioned. The solver time step $\Delta \tilde{t}_{\text{solver}}$ controls the numerical advancement of the OpenFOAM simulation, and the write interval $\Delta \tilde{t}_{\text{write}}$ determines how frequently flow-field snapshots are exported to the SmartRedis database. Parallel execution with MPI ranks introduces a natural spatial partitioning, with each domain decomposition contributing one block of the global snapshot. Thus, the number of MPI ranks N_{ranks} also determines the number of partitions in space (row-partitioning) of the snapshot matrix. The batch size b specifies how many consecutive snapshots are grouped together before being incorporated into the incremental SVD, and r is the SVD truncation rank. Finally, the simulation end time \tilde{t}_{end} defines the overall duration over which snapshots are collected.

4.3.1. Flow across a cylinder in 2D

The first test case used is the flow past a circular cylinder in two dimensions. This configuration is one of the most extensively studied benchmarks in CFD and is described in Chapter 3.

Test set-up

The geometry and computational mesh are shown in Fig. 3.3 and Fig. 3.2, respectively. The boundary conditions are described in Sec. 3.1.1, but here, the cylinder remains stationary with $\omega = 0$ (non-actuated). The k -th snapshot \mathbf{x}_k is built by vertically stacking the normalized field values as,

$$\mathbf{x}_k = [\tilde{p}, \tilde{u}_x, \tilde{u}_y]^T,$$

where the normalized pressure and velocity fields are computed using Eq. 4.1 with reference velocity u_{ref} . The input parameters for the partitioned SVD evaluation are listed in Table 4.1. For this study, multiple batch sizes are tested ($b = 40$ and $b = 100$) to examine sensitivity to the batch size.

Table 4.1.: Input parameters for the 2D cylinder partitioned SVD study

Parameter	Value	Description
Write interval, $\Delta\tilde{t}_{write}$	0.1	Time between successive snapshots written to the database.
Solver time step, $\Delta\tilde{t}_{solver}$	0.01	Numerical time step used by OpenFOAM.
Number of MPI ranks, N_{ranks}	4	Number of spatial partitions from domain decomposition.
SVD truncation rank, r	40	Number of retained POD modes.
End time, \tilde{t}_{end}	40	Total simulation duration.
Batch size, b	40, 100	Number of snapshots processed per SVD update.
Start time, \tilde{t}_0	0	Start time for snapshot matrix.
Reference velocity, u_{ref}	1.0	-

Memory requirements

To gauge the benefits of the partitioned SVD algorithm, the memory requirements are examined. For the 2D cylinder test case, the memory requirements of the snapshot matrix are estimated explicitly. The computational mesh contains 21,250 cells, and, for each snapshot, the state vector is constructed by stacking pressure and the two velocity components, $\mathbf{x}_k = [p, u_x, u_y]^T$, so that each snapshot has $3 \times 21,250 = 63,750$ degrees of freedom. There are 400 snapshots in total (for $\tilde{t}_{end} = 40$, $\Delta\tilde{t}_{write} = 0.1$ and snapshots starting from $\tilde{t} = 0$). The resulting snapshot matrix $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{63,750 \times 400}$ therefore contains $63,750 \times 400 = 25.5 \times 10^6$ entries. Assuming double precision (8 bytes per entry), storing the full snapshot matrix alone requires about $25.5 \times 10^6 \times 8 \approx 2.04 \times 10^8$ bytes, i.e. approximately 204 MB of memory.

For a rank- r truncated SVD with $r = 40$, the reduced factors contain approximately $m \cdot r = 63,750 \times 40 = 2.55 \times 10^6$ entries for \mathbf{U}_r , $r^2 = 1.6 \times 10^3$ entries for \mathbf{D}_r , and $n \cdot r = 400 \times 40 = 1.6 \times 10^4$ entries for \mathbf{V}_r .

In double precision this corresponds to approximately 20.4 MB for \mathbf{U}_r , 0.013 MB for \mathbf{D}_r , and 0.128 MB for \mathbf{V}_r , i.e. about 20.5 MB for the truncated factors in total. So, the total memory required is around

$$204 \text{ MB } (\mathbf{X}) + 20.5 \text{ MB } (\mathbf{U}_r, \mathbf{D}_r, \mathbf{V}_r) \approx 225 \text{ MB},$$

Other memory requirements that may be needed within the SVD computation are ignored. In contrast, the partitioned SVD algorithm does not store the full snapshot matrix in memory. Instead, it processes batches of size b snapshots at a time. For example, with $b = 100$ the batch matrix

$\mathbf{X}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{63,750 \times 100}$ contains 6.375×10^6 entries and thus requires about 51 MB, while $b = 40$ corresponds to 2.55×10^6 entries and about 20.4 MB. The total memory required for the partitioned algorithm is roughly,

$$\text{for } b = 100 : \quad 51 \text{ MB (batch)} + 20.5 \text{ MB } (\mathbf{U}_r, \mathbf{D}_r, \mathbf{V}_r) \approx 72 \text{ MB},$$

$$\text{for } b = 40 : \quad 20.4 \text{ MB (batch)} + 20.5 \text{ MB } (\mathbf{U}_r, \mathbf{D}_r, \mathbf{V}_r) \approx 41 \text{ MB}.$$

Compared to the ~ 225 MB required by the direct approach, the partitioned method reduces memory usage by a factor of 3 – 5 in the case of a 2D cylinder. Larger benefits can be seen with larger datasets, as in three-dimensional simulations.

Results

The singular values computed using the Partitioned SVD and the *Direct SVD* method are compared in Fig. 4.1. Excellent agreement is observed between the two cases, demonstrating that the Partitioned SVD algorithm accurately computes the SVD spectrum. This is true for both the batch sizes that were tested, i.e., $b = 100$ and $b = 40$. The results for the batch size $b = 40$ are not shown here, as they remain almost identical. This shows that the algorithm is insensitive to the batch size when it is greater than or equal to the chosen truncation rank. The current implementation does not support batch sizes smaller than the truncation rank.

Table 4.2.: Relative reconstruction error ε_{rec} for different batch sizes b .

Batch size b	Relative error ε_{rec}
40	1.743e-3
100	1.519e-3

The relative reconstruction errors are summarized in Table 4.2. For both batch sizes, the errors are of the order 10^{-3} , which show a perfect agreement between the direct and partitioned reconstructions. These differences are small enough to be attributed to floating-point round-off effects.

The reconstructed fields are subsequently written back into OpenFOAM using the *svdToFoam* utility, and the lift and drag coefficients were evaluated using the *forceCoeffs* function object (see Section 4.2.2). The comparison shown in Fig. 4.2 shows an excellent match between the force coefficients obtained from the original simulation and those computed from the reconstructed fields. This shows that the *svdToFoam* post-processing workflow operates as intended. Here, only the results for batch size $b = 100$ are shown as the difference is negligible for $b = 40$.

Figure 4.1.: Comparison of singular values computed using partitioned SVD and direct SVD for $b = 100$

4.3.2. Turbulent flow across cylinder in 3D

Turbulent flow past a circular cylinder in three dimensions has been extensively studied, with its characteristic features well documented in the literature [11]. The richness and complexity of the resulting flow, makes this configuration an ideal test case for evaluating the Partitioned SVD method on more complex datasets. The numerical setup used in the present work is taken from the publicly available GitHub repository [27], developed as part of prior research to conduct modal analysis on flow problems.

Numerical set-up

The three-dimensional setup considered here corresponds to a Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS) of turbulent flow past a circular cylinder at $Re = 3900$. The geometry is similar to the two-dimensional cylinder configuration but extruded in the spanwise (z) direction and refined sufficiently to resolve the turbulent scales. The inlet velocity is prescribed as $u_x = u_{\text{inlet}} = 39 \text{ m/s}$, with cylinder diameter $d = 0.1 \text{ m}$ and kinematic viscosity $\nu = 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, hence the Reynolds number is,

$$Re = \frac{u_{\text{inlet}} d}{\nu} = 3900.$$

The corresponding convective time scale is,

$$t_{\text{conv}} = \frac{d}{u_{\text{inlet}}} = \frac{0.1}{39.0} \approx 2.56 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s},$$

Figure 4.2.: Comparison of original and reconstructed force coefficients over time for $b = 100$

and all times in the following are non-dimensionalised as $\tilde{t} = t/t_{\text{conv}}$.

The computational domain extends $24d$ in the streamwise direction, $20d$ in the crossflow direction, and πd in the spanwise direction. The cylinder of radius $d = 0.1$ m is centred at $(x, y) = (8d, 10d)$. Periodic boundary conditions are applied in the spanwise direction for both velocity and pressure. A no-slip condition is imposed at the cylinder surface, the inflow prescribes a uniform velocity u_{inlet} , and slip (zero normal gradient) conditions are used at the top and bottom boundaries. A fixed pressure condition is enforced at the outlet.

The mesh, shown in Fig. 4.3, is generated using the *blockMesh* utility of OpenFOAM and contains approximately 9.4 million cells. The resolution is chosen to adequately resolve the turbulent structures in the near wake so that a DNS-quality solution is obtained. The setup follows the guidelines of Lehmkuhl et al. [11].

Partitioned SVD set-up

For the current simulation, it is observed that the initial transient decays after approximately 75 CTU, corresponding to $t \approx 0.19225$ s. Data used for the modal analysis are therefore collected only after this point. The data for the snapshot matrix is collected up to about 114 CTU, which corresponds to roughly 25 vortex-shedding cycles based on the lift coefficient. The input parameters used for the partitioned SVD algorithm are listed in Table 4.3. A write interval of $\Delta\tilde{t}_{\text{write}} = 0.195$ results in a total of 200 snapshots, with starting and ending non-dimensional times $\tilde{t}_0 = 74.975$ and $\tilde{t}_{\text{end}} = 113.9775$, respectively. Using a batch size of $b = 50$ leads to four SVD updates in the Partitioned SVD routine. The k -th snapshot \mathbf{x}_k is built by vertically stacking the normalized field values as,

$$\mathbf{x}_k = [\tilde{p}, \tilde{u}_x, \tilde{u}_y, \tilde{u}_z]^T,$$

Figure 4.3.: A cut-section view of the computational mesh for flow past cylinder in 3D. The inset shows a zoomed view near the cylinder boundary.

where the normalized pressure and velocity fields are computed using Eq. 4.1 with reference velocity u_{ref} . Because both the OpenFOAM simulation and the subsequent SVD evaluations are computationally and memory intensive, the workflow is deployed on an HPC system using *slurm* as the launcher (see Sec. 4.1). As a result, the SmartRedis database is created on the cluster nodes, and the specific database parameters that are used to deploy it on the TU Dresden Barnard clusters are listed in Table 4.4.

Table 4.3.: Input parameters for the 3D cylinder partitioned SVD study, for the descriptions refer to Table. 4.1

Parameter	Value
Write interval, $\Delta\tilde{t}_{write}$	0.195
Solver time step, $\Delta\tilde{t}_{solver}$	0.0039
Number of MPI ranks, N_{ranks}	100
SVD truncation rank, r	30
End time, \tilde{t}_{end}	113.9775
Batch size, b	50
Start time, \tilde{t}_0	74.9775
Reference velocity, u_{ref}	39.0

Table 4.4.: Database configuration parameters used for the SmartSim database setup.

Parameter	Value
Number of database nodes (db_nodes)	1
Batch mode (batch)	True
Network interface (interface)	ib2.0002
Tasks per node (tasks-per-node)	1
CPUs per task (cpus-per-task)	104

Memory requirements

For the 3D cylinder test case, the computational mesh contains approximately 9.4×10^6 cells. With pressure and all three velocity components included in the state vector, $\mathbf{x}_k = [p, u_x, u_y, u_z]^T$, each snapshot has

$$4 \times 9.4 \times 10^6 \approx 3.76 \times 10^7$$

degrees of freedom, i.e. $m \approx 37.6 \times 10^6$. The number of snapshots is 200, so that the snapshot matrix $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n} \approx \mathbb{R}^{37.6 \times 10^6 \times 200}$ contains

$$m \cdot n \approx 37.6 \times 10^6 \times 200 \approx 7.56 \times 10^9$$

entries. In double precision, this corresponds to $7.56 \times 10^9 \times 8 \approx 6.05 \times 10^{10}$ bytes, i.e. about 60 GB just to store \mathbf{X} . For a rank- r truncated SVD with $r = 30$, the reduced factors $\mathbf{U}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times r}$, $\mathbf{D}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$, and $\mathbf{V}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$. This corresponds to approximately $m \cdot r \approx 37.6 \times 10^6 \times 30 \approx 1.13 \times 10^9$ entries for \mathbf{U}_r , $r^2 = 900$ entries for \mathbf{D}_r , and $n \cdot r = 200 \times 30 = 6,000$ entries for \mathbf{V}_r .

In double precision, this corresponds to roughly 9.0 GB for \mathbf{U}_r and only a few kB for \mathbf{D}_r and \mathbf{V}_r , so that the truncated factors require about 9 GB in total. The direct approach, therefore, needs on the order of

$$60 \text{ GB } (\mathbf{X}) + 9 \text{ GB } (\mathbf{U}_r, \mathbf{D}_r, \mathbf{V}_r) \approx 69 \text{ GB},$$

again neglecting any additional working memory used inside the SVD routine. In contrast, the partitioned SVD with batch size $b = 50$ processes the t -th batch $\mathbf{X}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times b}$, which contains

$$m \cdot b \approx 37.6 \times 10^6 \times 50 \approx 1.88 \times 10^9$$

entries and thus requires about $1.88 \times 10^9 \times 8 \approx 1.50 \times 10^{10}$ bytes, i.e. roughly 15 GB, for the batch matrix. Together with the ~ 9 GB needed for the truncated factors, the total memory required for the Partitioned algorithm is about

$$15 \text{ GB } (\text{batch}) + 9 \text{ GB } (\mathbf{U}_r, \mathbf{D}_r, \mathbf{V}_r) \approx 24 \text{ GB}.$$

Compared to the ~ 69 GB required by the direct approach, the partitioned SVD reduces the peak memory usage by a factor of about 3 for the 3D cylinder dataset, while the absolute amount of memory saved is in the order of tens of gigabytes.

Results

As computing the SVD of the full snapshot matrix using the *direct* method is expensive due to memory limitations, only the results obtained from the partitioned SVD algorithm are presented here. Fig. 4.4 shows the resulting singular values, which behave as expected; the dominant modes contain most of the energy, while the remaining values decay rapidly and approach zero. The corresponding dominant pressure and resultant-velocity modes are shown in Figs. 4.5 and 4.6, respectively.

Due to an unresolved issue with *svdToFoam* on the HPC system, the modes could not be written directly in OpenFOAM format. Here, they are visualised using a Python script that uses the global left singular vectors and extracts a slice at the mid-span (halfway between the spanwise domain limits).

Figure 4.4.: Comparison of singular values computed using partitioned SVD and direct SVD for $b = 100$

Figure 4.5.: First four pressure modes computed using the partitioned SVD, visualised at the mid-span (halfway) section.

Figure 4.6.: First four resultant-velocity modes ($U_{\text{res}} = u_x^2 + u_y^2 + u_z^2$) computed using the partitioned SVD, visualised at the mid-span (halfway) section.

5. Reduced Order Modeling with DMDC

This chapter discusses strategies for constructing a robust reduced-order model using Dynamic Mode Decomposition with control for a given flow configuration. The overall goal of the project is to use this ROM as the environment within a Deep Reinforcement Learning loop. Using a ROM in place of full OpenFOAM simulations significantly reduces computational expenses and simulation time, but at the cost of reduced accuracy compared to high-fidelity CFD simulations.

As introduced in Sec. 2.2.2, the DMDC framework is particularly useful in systems with actuation. It separates the underlying unforced flow dynamics from the dynamics induced by actuation, enabling predictions for different actuation inputs. A DMDC model is created by using training data from a particular signal. As a result, the behavior of the *training signal* plays a crucial role in determining the DMDC model's robustness. Ideally, the DMDC model should perform fairly well across a broader set of actuation scenarios.

The flow configuration considered in this study is a two-dimensional flow past a cylinder actuated using a prescribed angular velocity (details provided in Sec. 3.1.1). The overall workflow for building and evaluating a DMDC model is illustrated in Fig. 5.1. First, the desired actuation signals are generated using Python. These signals are then supplied to an OpenFOAM simulation, which produces the corresponding flow fields. The resulting flow snapshots, together with the actuation history, are used to train the DMDC model. Model-specific hyperparameters are selected and tuned, and the predictive performance of the trained models is then assessed.

In the context of integrating the ROM into the DRL loop, two predictions are mainly important:

1. **Field quantities**, pressure & velocity, and
2. **Force coefficients**, namely the lift and drag acting on the cylinder.

5.1. Library of Signals

A library of actuation signals is constructed to generate a set of distinct DMDC models, which are later evaluated for predictive performance. All signals are generated in Python and subsequently exported as csv files, which serve as inputs to the corresponding OpenFOAM simulations.

The flow configuration considered in this work employs a single actuation mode: an angular velocity ω imposed on a two-dimensional cylinder (see Sec. 3.1.1). The chosen set of signals comprises several commonly used excitation types, selected to span different levels of temporal complexity.

To ensure consistency across the entire signal library, all actuation signals have the same duration and identical amplitude limits. In every case, the actuation is strictly zero over the initial interval

Figure 5.1.: Workflow followed to evaluate DMDc models

$\tilde{t} \in [0, 40]$ CTU. This allows the flow to develop sufficiently before the actuation begins. In general, this portion of the trajectory, where $\omega = 0$, is either completely omitted or only a small portion is retained, depending on the specific training setup. After $\tilde{t} = 40$ CTU, the actuation signal varies within the prescribed amplitude bounds, ensuring consistent forcing conditions across all cases in the library.

The non-dimensional actuation (angular velocity) is defined as

$$\tilde{\omega} = \frac{\omega}{\omega_{\max}},$$

where ω_{\max} denotes the amplitude limit of the actuation. Following previous studies [7], $\omega_{\max} = 5$ rad/s is set. Consequently, the bounds for the dimensional and non-dimensional actuation are

$$\omega \in [-5, 5] \text{ rad/s}, \quad \tilde{\omega} \in [-1, 1].$$

The selected signals are described in the following sections.

1. **Random Walk.** This signal tests whether the DMDc model can reproduce irregular, non-periodic fluctuations. The signal values are sampled uniformly within the actuation limits and connected via spline interpolation. This method ensures the signal remains smooth, minimiz-

ing sharp changes that are challenging for DMDc.

2. **Chirp Signal.** The chirp provides a smoothly varying instantaneous frequency over a prescribed frequency band. A periodic chirp signal is generated to avoid sharp discontinuities that may occur in a piecewise assembled chirp signal. This is done using the normalized phase,

$$\tau = \frac{t \bmod T}{T},,$$

where T is the duration of one full actuation period and \bmod denotes the modulo operator, mapping the time t onto the interval $[0, T)$. Then, the signal is given by

$$\omega(t) = A \sin(\theta(t)), \quad \theta(t) = 2\pi N \left(\phi + \frac{m}{2\pi} \sin(2\pi\phi) \right),$$

with

$$N = f_{\text{avg}} T, \quad f_{\text{avg}} = \frac{f_{\text{min}} + f_{\text{max}}}{2}, \quad m = \frac{f_{\text{max}} - f_{\text{min}}}{f_{\text{max}} + f_{\text{min}}}.$$

The corresponding instantaneous frequency is

$$f(t) = f_{\text{avg}} [1 + m \cos(2\pi\phi)].$$

3. **Chirp with Varying Amplitude.** A piecewise-constant amplitude envelope $A(t)$ is applied to the chirp signal, producing,

$$\omega(t) = A(t) \sin(\theta(t)).$$

4. **Amplitude-Modulated Signal (AM).** This excitation combines smooth amplitude and frequency modulation. With the normalized phase $\tau = (t \bmod T)/T$, where T is the modulation period, the amplitude envelope is

$$A(\phi) = A_0 [1 + m_{\text{AM}} \cos(2\pi\phi)],$$

where m_{AM} is the amplitude-modulation depth. The frequency-modulated phase uses the modulation index m_{FM} ,

$$\theta(t) = 2\pi N \left(\phi + \frac{m_{\text{FM}}}{2\pi} \sin(2\pi\phi) \right),$$

yielding the AM excitation

$$\omega(t) = A(\phi) \sin(\theta(t)).$$

For a more detailed description and implementation details, the reader is referred to the GitHub repository [20].

(a) Random-walk actuation signal.

(b) Periodic chirp signal.

(c) Chirp with piecewise-varying amplitude.

(d) Amplitude-modulated (AM) periodic signal.

Figure 5.2.: Actuation signals used to train the DMDc models

5.1.1. OpenFOAM Simulation

The time series generated in the previous section is exported to a *csv* file (here it is named *omega.csv*) with two columns: the first column contains the time (in s) and the second column the corresponding actuation value $\omega(t)$ in rad/s. This file is placed in the case directory and specifies the angular velocity of the cylinder. The rotation is imposed via the *rotatingWallVelocity* boundary condition, where the angular velocity is read directly from the *csv* file and is treated as a piecewise linearly interpolated function over time. The boundary-condition block that is used in `0.org/U` is given in Listing 5.1.

```
cylinder
{
  type rotatingWallVelocity;
  origin (0.2 0.2 0);
  axis (0 0 1);

  omega csvFile;
  omegaCoeffs
  {
    nHeaderLine 1; // one header line in omega.csv
    refColumn 0; // time column
    componentColumns (1); // column (scalar)
    separator ",";
    mergeSeparators no;
    file "omega.csv";
    outOfBounds clamp; // clamp | repeat | warn
    interpolationScheme linear; // piecewise-linear interpolation in time
  }
}
```

Listing 5.1: OpenFOAM boundary condition for the cylinder rotation using a CSV-based time-varying angular velocity.

5.2. Fitting the DMDc Model

To build the DMDc model, the flow-field data from a simulation is loaded using *FOAMDataLoader*, a tool from the *flowTorch* library [28, 30]. The velocity and pressure snapshots from each simulation are assembled into a state matrix, which, together with the corresponding actuation signal, serves as the input for fitting the DMDc model. The *PyDMD* library [3, 4, 8] is used for this purpose, from which the linear operators that advance the state based on the actuation are extracted. The formulation for adding time delays and then making predictions using the obtained operators is described in Sec. 2.2.4. These predicted fields are then converted into OpenFOAM field files using the *svdToFoam* utility (Sec. 4.2.1), after which force coefficients such as drag and lift are evaluated using OpenFOAM post-processing routines (Sec. 4.2.2). These models are then tested using the

procedures described in the following section.

5.2.1. Model-specific studies

The fitting of the DMDc model involves several hyper-parameters, such as the snapshot truncation rank η , the DMDc truncation rank κ , and the number of time delays q . To simplify the parameter study, the snapshot and DMDc truncation ranks are set equal:

$$\eta = \kappa = r.$$

This assumption could be justified because the DMDc basis is computed from the delay-embedded snapshot matrix, which already exists in the reduced POD space defined by \mathbf{U}_η . If the POD basis is sufficiently expressive, then choosing an identical truncation for the DMDc operators avoids introducing mismatches between the two subspaces.

With this, only two hyper-parameters remain: truncation rank r and number of time delays q . To evaluate the effect of these parameters, a few metrics are computed and are described in the following paragraphs.

For these assessments, the available snapshot data is divided into *train* and *test* subsets. Each snapshot \mathbf{x}_k is constructed by vertically stacking the normalized flow-field quantities,

$$\mathbf{x}_k = [\tilde{p}, \tilde{u}_x, \tilde{u}_y]^\top. \quad (5.1)$$

where the normalized pressure and velocity components are obtained using Eq. 4.1 with reference velocity $u_{\text{ref}} = 1$. The interval from $t = 40$ to $t = 90$ CTU is used for training, while the remaining snapshots from $t = 90$ to $t = 120$ CTU form the test set. This allows the model to be evaluated on both the data used for fitting and previously unseen flow states. Using the index sets I_{train} and I_{test} associated with the selected time intervals, the split is written as

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{train}} = \mathbf{X}[:, I_{\text{train}}], \quad (5.2)$$

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{test}} = \mathbf{X}[:, I_{\text{test}}]. \quad (5.3)$$

Using this setup, the following tests are performed on each model:

1. Projection Error. This test evaluates how well the snapshot-POD basis obtained from the training data, $\mathbf{U}_\eta = \mathbf{U}_r$, represents both the training snapshots $\mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}$ and the unseen test snapshots

\mathbf{X}_{test} . The POD basis is computed from the SVD of the training data,

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{train}} \approx \mathbf{U}_r \mathbf{D}_r \mathbf{V}_r^T. \quad (5.4)$$

The projection of the training and test data onto this basis is performed as

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{proj, train}} = \mathbf{U}_r \mathbf{U}_r^T \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}, \quad (5.5)$$

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{proj, test}} = \mathbf{U}_r \mathbf{U}_r^T \mathbf{X}_{\text{test}}. \quad (5.6)$$

The corresponding relative projection errors are defined as

$$E_{\text{proj, train}}(k) = \frac{\|\mathbf{X}_{\text{proj, train}}[:, k] - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}[:, k]\|_2}{\|\mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}[:, k]\|_2}, \quad (5.7)$$

$$E_{\text{proj, test}}(k) = \frac{\|\mathbf{X}_{\text{proj, test}}[:, k] - \mathbf{X}_{\text{test}}[:, k]\|_2}{\|\mathbf{X}_{\text{test}}[:, k]\|_2}. \quad (5.8)$$

where k denotes the time index at which the projection error is evaluated.

This metric establishes a lower bound on the accuracy achievable by the DMDc model constructed in the same reduced space, since the model cannot outperform the representational capacity of the POD basis itself. It therefore provides a guideline for selecting an appropriate truncation rank r .

2. Reconstruction and Prediction Errors. Once the DMDc operators have been identified using the training data, two error metrics are evaluated on both the training and testing intervals.

Reconstruction error measures how well the trained operators reproduce the trajectory used for training. To compute this, the first q time steps of the training data are used to initialize the delay-embedded state, after which the model rollout follows the procedure described in Sec. 2.2.4. Once the predicted states have been lifted back to the full space using Eq. 2.52, the resulting matrix $\mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}^{(\text{rec})}$ represents the reconstructed training trajectory.

Since the first q states are used only for initialisation and are not predicted, they are excluded from the error computation. A *time-wise reconstruction error* is therefore defined as

$$E_{\text{rec}}(k) = \frac{\|\mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}[:, k] - \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}^{(\text{rec})}[:, k]\|_2}{\|\mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}[:, k]\|_2}, \quad k = q, q + 1, \dots, \max(I_{\text{train}}). \quad (5.9)$$

where each $E_{\text{rec}}(k)$ measures the relative reconstruction error at a single time step.

Prediction error quantifies how accurately the model predicts an unseen portion of the trajectory.

Using the first q time steps from the test interval as the initial condition, the model is rolled out over the testing horizon, generating the predicted full-state matrix $\mathbf{X}_{\text{test}}^{(\text{pred})}$.

Analogous to reconstruction, a *time-wise prediction error* is defined as

$$E_{\text{pred}}(k) = \frac{\|\mathbf{X}_{\text{test}}[:, k] - \mathbf{X}_{\text{test}}^{(\text{pred})}[:, k]\|_2}{\|\mathbf{X}_{\text{test}}[:, k]\|_2}, \quad k = q, q + 1, \dots, \max(I_{\text{test}}). \quad (5.10)$$

which measures the relative prediction error at each time step of the test interval. This study considers two configurations: one with a time delay of $q = 100$ and one without time delay, i.e. $q = 0$. The overall formulation remains the same in both cases, the snapshot matrix is first reduced in dimension, but when $q = 0$, no delay augmentation is applied after the reduction step.

3. Mode coefficients — Reconstruction and Prediction. Analogous to the full-state reconstruction and prediction error, the reconstructed and predicted *mode coefficients* can also be compared against their original counterparts. The true (reference) mode coefficients for the training and test sets are obtained by projecting the corresponding state matrices onto the reduced basis:

$$\hat{\mathbf{X}}_{\text{train}} = \mathbf{U}_r^T \mathbf{X}_{\text{train}}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{X}}_{\text{test}} = \mathbf{U}_r^T \mathbf{X}_{\text{test}}.$$

The reconstructed and predicted mode coefficients are computed following the same procedure described in the Paragraph. 5.2.1, but by evaluating the mode coefficients using Eq. (2.50).

Each row of the mode-coefficient matrix represents the temporal evolution of a specific mode. Since the dominant modes capture the most energetic and dynamically relevant structures in the flow, their temporal coefficients heavily influence the overall prediction quality. Comparing the mode coefficients provides a low-dimensional and interpretable assessment of predictive performance.

Implementation. All validation tasks, including data loading, delay embedding, operator fitting, and error calculation, are implemented in the accompanying repository [20].

5.2.2. Results

The Fig. 5.3 shows the projection error computed using Eq. 5.8 for truncation ranks ranging from $r = 10$ to $r = 150$. The dotted vertical line marks the separation between the training and testing windows. For all signals, the projection error within the training interval decreases monotonically with increasing r . This behavior is expected as increasing the truncation rank enlarges the POD subspace constructed from the training data, and the snapshots used to build the basis are represented more accurately as more modes are retained. In terms of absolute magnitude, the projection error

Figure 5.3.: Projection error E_{proj} of the snapshot-POD basis on training and testing data for different ranks r ; the vertical line marks the train-test split.

is below 10% for all cases even at the lowest rank considered ($r = 10$), indicating that the dominant flow dynamics are captured even with a strongly truncated basis. Increasing the rank further leads to a reduction of the training error by up to one order of magnitude. In contrast, the projection error in the test window often plateaus beyond a certain truncation rank. This occurs because a basis constructed solely from training data can only represent new, unseen flow states to some extent. Once the dominant directions present in the test data have already been captured, adding additional training modes does not significantly improve the representation. The jump in error at the dotted line reflects this transition; in the test region, the model is effectively extrapolating, and extrapolation errors are naturally larger than interpolation errors. This behavior is observed for most actuation signals, except for the chirp signal. For the chirp case, both the training and testing projection errors decrease similarly as r increases. This can be attributed to the fact that the testing

portion of the periodic chirp closely resembles the training portion (Fig. 5.2), meaning the POD basis derived from the training window remains representative throughout the entire trajectory.

Figure 5.4.: Reconstruction error E_{rec} with and without delay embedding ($q = 100$) for each control signal. The vertical line marks the start of the prediction horizon.

A larger absolute magnitude of the test projection error is observed in random walk and chirp with varying amplitude signals, indicating a less structured dynamics that is more difficult to represent. In general, a truncation rank of around $r = 50$ seems reasonable, as beyond this rank the reduction in error is not significant. Choosing a smaller truncation rank is computationally beneficial, as building the time-delayed matrices results in smaller matrices.

The reconstruction and prediction errors for the different actuation signals are shown in Figs. 5.4 and 5.5. Each plot also compares two cases, one using a delay embedding with $q = 100$, and another with no embedding ($q = 0$). These two values are selected to highlight the effect of incorporating time delays by contrasting it with case where there is no delay. The value $q = 100$ is chosen to be sufficiently large to assess the maximum benefit that can be obtained from time-delay embedding. In general, incorporating time delays reduces reconstruction error, though the improvement is modest. For the Random Walk input, there is essentially no visible gain when using a time delay,

although the reconstruction errors are already significantly smaller than those observed for the other actuation signals.

Figure 5.5.: Prediction error E_{pred} with and without delay embedding ($q = 100$) for each control signal; the vertical line marks the start of the prediction horizon.

The behavior of the prediction error follows a similar trend; the use of time delays yields a clear improvement for all signals except the Random Walk input, where there is no real benefit. The prediction errors are generally larger than the corresponding reconstruction errors and often increase with time. When a time delay of $q = 100$ is used, the errors for all actuation signals lie within the same order of magnitude, whereas in the absence of time-delay embedding the error magnitudes vary substantially across signals. This trend is observed for both reconstruction and prediction errors, indicating that the inclusion of time delays has a stabilizing effect on the model performance. Additional insight is provided by examining the dominant mode-coefficient trajectories shown in Sec. A.4. These plots allow the assessment of prediction quality directly in the reduced-order space. For most signals, the predicted mode-coefficient dynamics improve significantly when time delays are included, with the Random Walk signal being the only exception where the predictions remain nearly unchanged. Mode-coefficient analysis is useful because it isolates the prediction quality itself, without the influence of projection errors, thereby separating the contributions of the two error

sources.

An additional observation from the study is that a relatively large number of delays is required to achieve stable and accurate results. Using too few delays sometimes leads to unstable predictions. This may occur because the timestep is too small and consecutive snapshots are highly correlated; stacking them to form the augmented matrix can yield rank-deficient or poorly conditioned matrices. One way to alleviate this issue is to embed only every n -th snapshot, rather than using all adjacent samples. This can reduce collinearity in the delayed snapshot matrices and improve their numerical conditioning. The suitability of the different actuation signals for building generalizable models can be judged based on the prediction error in the test window. The chirp and amplitude-modulated signals show the lowest prediction errors; however, this may be misleading, as their periodic nature implies that the test data are likely well represented within the training interval. The random walk and chirp with varying amplitude inputs show moderately higher prediction errors, but remain below approximately 15%, indicating reasonable generalization. So, given the limited differences in error magnitude and the varying nature of the excitations, it is difficult to identify a single actuation signal that clearly yields the most generalizable model. Overall, for the present modeling setup, a truncation rank of $r = 60$ combined with a delay embedding of $q = 100$ seems to be a reasonable choice, even though this configuration does not perform equally well for all actuation signals.

5.3. Library-based DMDc

Following the model-specific performance studies, the DMDc models must ultimately be integrated to advance the flow state in time under a given control input. When the agent explores new control policies, the resulting actuation is typically stochastic and spans a wide range of the control space. Under such conditions, relying on a single DMDc model trained on a fixed actuation signal is generally insufficient. While such a model may be locally accurate, it remains biased toward the dynamics represented in its training data.

Instead, all DMDc models from the library are employed during prediction. A simple and effective strategy to achieve this is to randomly shuffle among the available DMDc models over consecutive prediction windows. This approach is referred to as *Multi-Operator Random Shuffling* (MORS), and its formulation is described in Sec. 2.2.5. The underlying motivation is that a single linear reduced-order model is insufficient to capture the full variability of the underlying nonlinear dynamics. By switching between multiple DMDc models during prediction, the bias associated with any individual operator can be reduced. To enable consistent switching, the different snapshot matrices are expressed in the same reduced-order basis \mathcal{U}_r .

The performance of this approach is evaluated in the following sections.

5.3.1. Model validation approach

The predictive performance of the library-based DMDc framework is evaluated using a validation signal that is not included in the library of training signals. This validation input is taken from one of the actuation trajectories generated by the DRL controller in previous work [17]. The signal, shown in Fig. 5.6, is highly representative of the type of control inputs that the DMDc environment is expected to encounter in practice. The signals used to construct the model library are the same as those described in Sec. 5.1.

Figure 5.6.: Validation signal.

Reference data for this validation case is obtained by running a full-order OpenFOAM simulation with the corresponding actuation. The snapshot matrix is constructed in the same manner as described in Sec. 5.2.1. For the model fitting performed here, the data is taken from the time window $\tilde{t} = 30$ to $\tilde{t} = 120$. A truncation rank of $r = 60$ is used for all signals except the Random Walk input, for which a lower rank of $r = 40$ is employed. These truncation ranks are selected based on the studies from Sec. 5.2.2. The validation signal is then used to generate predictions from each individual DMDc model in the *library* as well as from the MORS model described in Algorithm 4. This allows a direct comparison of the predictive capabilities of each standalone model and the combined MORS approach. All predicted fields are written back to OpenFOAM using *svdToFoam*, and the resulting force coefficients are computed and compared against the reference simulation. In addition to force coefficients, a time-resolved relative error of the full state is evaluated. For each time instant k , the error is defined as

$$L_{\text{pred},k} = \frac{\|\mathbf{X}_{\text{ref}}[:,k] - \mathbf{X}_{\text{pred}}[:,k]\|_2}{\|\mathbf{X}_{\text{ref}}[:,k]\|_2}. \quad (5.11)$$

where $\mathbf{X}_{\text{ref}}[:,k]$ and $\mathbf{X}_{\text{pred}}[:,k]$ denote the reference and predicted full-state vectors at time index k .

Since a common reduced basis is used for projecting all signals onto the *reduced snapshot* subspace, the corresponding projection error for a given signal can be defined as follows. Let \mathbf{X}_i denote the snapshot matrix associated with signal i , and let \mathbf{U}_r be the common reduced basis obtained from the entire library of signals. The time-varying *common-subspace projection error* is then given by

$$E_{\text{proj, com}}^{(i)}(k) = \frac{\left\| \mathbf{X}_i[:, k] - \mathbf{U}_r \mathbf{U}_r^\top \mathbf{X}_i[:, k] \right\|_2}{\left\| \mathbf{X}_i[:, k] \right\|_2}. \quad (5.12)$$

In addition, a second projection occurs, while fitting the DMDc model using the delayed state matrices. This projection is based on the basis given in Eq. 2.47, where the delayed mode coefficients are projected into the *delay-embedded* subspace. For signal i , let the delay-embedded snapshot matrix be $\widehat{\mathbf{X}}_q^{(i)}$, and let $\widehat{\mathbf{U}}_r^{(i)}$ denote the truncated basis obtained from this delay-embedded data. The associated *delay-embedded* projection error is defined as

$$E_{\text{proj, aug}}^{(i)}(k) = \frac{\left\| \widehat{\mathbf{X}}_q^{(i)}[:, k] - \widehat{\mathbf{U}}_r^{(i)} \widehat{\mathbf{U}}_r^{(i)\top} \widehat{\mathbf{X}}_q^{(i)}[:, k] \right\|_2}{\left\| \widehat{\mathbf{X}}_q^{(i)}[:, k] \right\|_2}. \quad (5.13)$$

5.3.2. Results

The *common-subspace* projection errors for the different signals are shown in Fig. 5.7, with truncation ranks ranging from $r = 10$ to $r = 150$. Since the actuation begins at $\tilde{t} = 40$ CTU, the interval between $\tilde{t} = 30$ and $\tilde{t} = 40$ correspond to an unactuated flow and are therefore identical for all signals. In this interval, the projection error decreases gradually up to the onset of actuation, after which a sharp increase is observed. This trend is consistent across all signals and truncation ranks. Overall, the snapshot matrices are well represented by the common basis. Among all signals, the highest projection error is observed for the chirp signal with varying amplitude, although the error decays subsequently. The projection error obtained using the common POD basis is generally higher than the projection error observed in the training region when using individual POD bases, as shown in Fig. 5.3, particularly at higher truncation ranks. In the test region, however, the projection errors for both approaches are comparable over the considered range of truncation ranks, with the absolute error magnitude being on the order of 10^{-2} . Although increasing the truncation rank is expected to further reduce the projection error associated with the common POD basis. A common-basis truncation rank of approximately $r = 60$ appears sufficient, yielding projection errors on the order of 10^{-2} .

The *delay-embedded* projection errors, computed using Eq. 5.13, are presented in Fig. A.10. The truncation ranks employed here correspond to those listed in Sec. 5.3.1. A pronounced spike in projection error is observed at the initial time steps. This arises from the manner in which *PyDMD*

constructs the DMDc basis: it relies on the one-step-shifted matrix described in Eq. 2.47, and consequently, the very first time instance is not included in the basis and is effectively extrapolated. This is precisely why the fitting window is chosen to begin at $\tilde{t} = 30$, ensuring that this initial extrapolation error is displaced away from the important actuation interval starting at $\tilde{t} = 40$. Across the remainder of the time domain, the delay-embedded projection error remains largely stable.

Figure 5.7.: Projection error $E_{\text{proj,com}}$ of the common POD basis on the fitting data from different signals for different ranks r ; the actuation starts at $\tilde{t} = 40$ CTU. The error is computed using Eq. 5.12.

The force-coefficient predictions for the validation signal using each individual model in the library are shown in Fig. 5.8 and Fig. 5.10. Among the individual models, the Random Walk trained model performs best. This is likely because the validation signal itself exhibits non-periodic, fluctuating behavior, which could make the dynamics easier to predict as the training data is similar.

In contrast, the model trained on the Chirp signal tends to overpredict the drag coefficient. This

behavior is consistent with the mean drag level present in the original Chirp simulation (Fig. A.9), indicating that the model predictions tend to drift towards the force-coefficient value on which each operator was trained. Such a bias is not observed for the Chirp with varying amplitude model; in this case, the predictions remain closer to the validation signal rather than reverting toward the original training force coefficient characteristics. This suggests that introducing amplitude variations in the training signal helps the model adapt to changes in the mean drag level and improves robustness. Both the Random Walk and AM signals also produce predictions with mean drag values close to those of the reference simulation, coincidentally similar to those of the validation signal, which contributes to their strong performance. However, it remains unclear how well these models would generalize if the target trajectory's mean drag were significantly different. These effects are even more evident in the lift coefficient predictions as seen from the original signal coefficients shown in Fig. A.11. In the validation trajectory, the lift force exhibits a noticeable dip in amplitude between 50 – 60 CTU, followed by an increase. Among the individual models, only the Chirp with varying amplitude model captures this trend. The plain Chirp model again performs the worst, consistent with its inability to capture amplitude changes.

The performance of the MORS model is shown in Figs. 5.11 and 5.12. With a shuffling frequency of $n_{\text{shuf}} = 1$ as shown in Fig. 5.11, the drag prediction oscillates rapidly between the biases of the individual models, resulting in a highly jagged curve. The lift prediction, however, remains relatively reasonable. Increasing the shuffling interval to $n_{\text{shuf}} = 10$ as shown in Fig. 5.12, yields much smoother and more interpretable predictions, as the influence of each model lasts long enough to avoid rapid switching. Nevertheless, the MORS model does not capture the mid-trajectory dip in lift amplitude either, as most constituent models fail to represent it. The time-resolved relative error of the full-state prediction (Fig. 5.9) confirms these observations: the Random Walk model performs best overall, the Chirp model performs worst, while the AM model lies in between. The Chirp with varying amplitude model begins with a low error but exhibits increasing deviation over time. Although the overall prediction error may not be the most informative metric, what is important is whether the model is able to capture the underlying dynamics of the system. The MORS model balances the behaviors of all individual models and consistently produces error levels near the middle of the range, as expected from aggregating multiple biased predictors.

Figure 5.8.: Comparison of drag coefficients C_d computed from fields predicted using different library-based DMDc models. The actuation corresponds to the DRL signal shown in Fig. 5.2. The results are compared against the original force coefficients obtained from OpenFOAM.

Figure 5.9.: Time-varying prediction error of the flow field, evaluated using Eq. 5.11, for the library of actuation signals. The error is computed for flow fields predicted using different library-based DMDc models

Figure 5.10.: Comparison of lift coefficients C_l predicted using different library-based DMDc models. All results correspond to the library of signals and are compared to the original OpenFOAM force data for the same actuation.

Figure 5.11.: Force coefficients reconstructed using the MORS model with a shuffling interval of $n_{\text{shuf}} = 1$. The actuation corresponds to the library of signals, and the results are compared to the original OpenFOAM force data.

Figure 5.12.: Force coefficients reconstructed using the MORS model with a shuffling interval of $n_{\text{shuf}} = 10$. The actuation corresponds to the library of signals, and the results are compared to the original OpenFOAM simulation.

6. Integration of ROM into DRL

This chapter describes the integration of the reduced-order model into the deep reinforcement learning framework as implemented in the *drlfoam* repository [17]. The flow configuration used for testing is the flow past a circular cylinder in 2D, as introduced in Chapter 3. The ROM is based on the DMDc models constructed in Chapter 5. The simulation starts from an initial unactuated transient phase from $\tilde{t} = 0$ to 40 CTU, after which active control is enabled. The objective of the controller is to reduce the drag and suppress lift fluctuations according to the reward definition given in Eq. 3.1.

The DRL agent learns a control law through repeated interaction with the environment. The control law maps observed flow measurements to a control action, which in the present case corresponds to the angular velocity of the rotating cylinder. This mapping is represented by a stochastic policy $\pi_\theta(a | o)$, parameterized by the neural-network parameters θ . Here, a denotes the control action (cylinder angular velocity) and o denotes the observed state, represented by the vector of pressure probe values. The agent is initialized with a random policy and improved iteratively through training.

Each training iteration consists of a single *episode*, which corresponds to one complete roll-out of the environment over the actuation window $\tilde{t} \in [40, 80)$. The roll-out is performed on the snapshot representation in which the flow fields are stacked as defined in Eq. 5.1. This representation is referred to as the *snapshot state* to distinguish it from the state measurements obtained at the probe locations. At the beginning of each episode, the initial snapshot state is taken from the unactuated simulation and is identical for all episodes (or multiple initial states in the case of time-delayed embeddings). This initial state is then advanced in time using the DMDc model to generate a full sequence over the actuation window. After an episode completes, the policy is updated using the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm, and the updated policy is then used for the next episode. This procedure is repeated until the control performance converges.

6.1. Implementation

In the present work, the roll-out in the environment is implemented using a Python-based framework, in which the ROM advances the flow state rather than the full OpenFOAM solver. A schematic overview of the coupled ROM-DRL workflow is shown in Fig. 6.1.

At each discrete time step k within an episode, the agent observes pressure values sampled at a set of fixed probe locations

$$\mathcal{R}_p = \left\{ \mathbf{r}_p^{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{r}_p^{(N_p)} \right\}.$$

where N_p represents the number of probes and \mathbf{r}_p is the position vector of the probe. The pressure

field predicted by the ROM is interpolated at these locations to form the probe observation vector

$$\mathbf{p}_{p,k} = \left[p_k(\mathbf{r}_p^{(1)}) \quad \dots \quad p_k(\mathbf{r}_p^{(N_p)}) \right]^T = C_p(\mathcal{R}_p, \mathbf{x}_k), \quad (6.1)$$

where $p_k(\mathbf{r})$ denotes the pressure field at time step k , and \mathbf{x}_k is the corresponding snapshot state vector. The interpolation operator C_p employs a K -nearest-neighbors approach combined with inverse-distance weighting.

The probe observations $\mathbf{p}_{p,k}$ are provided as input to the stochastic policy π_θ , which outputs the parameters (α_k, β_k) of a Beta distribution. The control action is sampled as

$$\omega_k \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_k, \beta_k),$$

and rescaled to the actuation bounds, which is $\omega \in [-5, 5]$ rad/s for the current flow configuration.

Given the applied control input, the snapshot state is advanced using MORS model (described in Sec. 2.2.5), according to

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \text{MORS}(\mathbf{x}_k, \omega_k). \quad (6.2)$$

This procedure is repeated for the entire actuation period, generating a trajectory of probe observations and control actions.

The predicted snapshot states are then stored in a SmartRedis database, which is converted into OpenFOAM format using *svdToFoam* and post-processed to evaluate the time histories of the drag and lift coefficients. The actuation history

$$\Omega = [\omega_0, \omega_1, \dots, \omega_{n-1}]$$

is also recorded.

The collected roll-out data are then provided to the agent, where the reward is evaluated, and subsequently the neural networks in the PPO algorithm are updated, resulting in an updated policy [7,24]. In the current implementation, the standard OpenFOAM solvers in *drfFoam* are replaced with a ROM-based Python workflow, and no changes are made to the controller logic.

6.2. DRL Setup and Performance

This section describes the DRL input parameters and discusses the corresponding simulation results.

Figure 6.1.: Workflow used to couple the controller and the environment. The loop represents the steps taken in one episode.

6.2.1. Simulation setup

The *drlfoam* framework requires several input parameters that define both the reinforcement learning setup and the environment. In particular, the parameters governing the neural networks used in the PPO update. One of the important hyperparameters is the learning rate of the policy network, as it directly influences the stability and convergence of the training process. In this study, different learning rates are tested to examine their effects on training behavior.

Several additional parameters are required, such as the neural network architecture, activation functions, and optimizer settings. These are kept identical to the default configuration provided in the *drlfoam* library to ensure consistency with previous studies. For a detailed description of these parameters, the reader is referred to [7, 24].

The buffer size, which defines the number of parallel environment instances (i.e. independent simulation copies) used to collect data during training, is set to 4 in the present study. Control actuation is initiated at $\tilde{t} = 40$ and applied until $\tilde{t} = 80$. The reduced-order model employed in the environment is based on the MORS framework described in Sec. 2.2.5, where a shuffling rate $n_{\text{shuf}} = 1$ is used, and the excitation signals used to construct the DMDc library are identical to those introduced in Sec. 5.1. The training loop is executed for over 80 episodes to assess the long-term behavior of the

learning process. The reward signal is computed according to Eq. 3.1.

To monitor training progress, an averaged reward R is computed for each episode by averaging the instantaneous rewards over all time steps of the roll-out and all the buffers. The corresponding standard deviation is evaluated over the same samples and reflects the variability within each episode.

6.2.2. Results

The simulation is first tested for different learning rates of the policy network, starting from relatively large values. It is observed that large learning rates, such as 10^{-2} , lead to unstable policy updates and cause the KL-divergence constraint in the PPO algorithm to be violated. The KL-divergence is a measure of the difference between successive policies. Based on these observations, a learning rate of 10^{-4} is selected, resulting in stable policy updates throughout training.

The Fig. 6.2 shows the evolution of the averaged reward R as a function of the training episodes. Ideally, the reward is expected to increase over successive episodes as the DRL agent learns a more optimal control policy that maximizes the reward. This behavior is observed in Model-Free DRL, where the data is obtained from previous work.

Figure 6.2.: Evolution of the averaged reward over training episodes for the model-free DRL case (left) and the DMDc-based case (right). The shaded region indicates the variability across episodes.

In contrast, results obtained with the DMDc-based environment show no noticeable improvement across training episodes. The averaged rewards remains nearly constant, indicating that the policy updates are negligible and the DRL algorithm fails to learn an effective control strategy. This behavior suggests that the applied control actuation has little to no influence on the reward function.

Further investigation supports this hypothesis. By comparing the drag and lift coefficients obtained

Figure 6.3.: Actuation signals ω_{act} generated by the DRL agent over the actuation window $\tilde{t} \in [40, 80)$ for two representative episodes. The signals correspond to Episode 1 and Episode 5

from different episodes, as shown in Fig. 6.4, it is observed that, despite significantly different actuation inputs (see Fig. 6.3), the resulting drag and lift histories are identical. During exploration, the actuation signal is highly fluctuating, so it is possible that the effects of successive control inputs may partially cancel each other before the model has sufficient time to develop a distinct dynamical response. As a consequence, the DMDc model becomes largely insensitive to rapid variations in the control input.

This behavior suggests that the influence of the control operator \mathbf{B} in the DMDc formulation is comparatively weak relative to the unforced dynamics. As a result, the system evolution is dominated by the operator \mathbf{A} , preventing the DRL agent from identifying a meaningful control strategy.

Figure 6.4.: Force coefficients recorded from two representative episodes. The results are from Episode 1 and Episode 5

7. Conclusion

This work investigated the use of a reduced order model as the environment in a deep reinforcement learning training loop. The ROM employed in this study is based on Dynamic Mode Decomposition with Control. Several components required to build this framework and integrate it with DRL were developed and evaluated.

First, the Partitioned SVD algorithm was implemented and validated for the two-dimensional flow past a circular cylinder by comparing its singular values with those obtained from the full snapshot matrix. The same approach was then successfully applied to the more memory-intensive three-dimensional cylinder flow, for which a direct SVD computation is impractical. In this case, the partitioned SVD enabled efficient computation of the singular value decomposition with relative ease. Using basic calculations, it was shown that at least 45 GB of memory could be saved, with even larger reductions achievable by decreasing the batch size.

Subsequently, the *svdToFoam* utility was extended to support the reconstruction of all relevant field types in OpenFOAM-readable formats. This extension serves as a key component of the overall workflow, enabling the conversion of ROM-predicted fields to OpenFOAM format and the subsequent evaluation of lift and drag coefficients using standard OpenFOAM post-processing utilities.

A library of DMDc models were constructed using commonly employed excitation signals, including random walk, chirp, chirp with varying amplitude, and amplitude-modulated inputs. Each signal was used to generate CFD data and train a corresponding DMDc model, which was then systematically evaluated for different truncation ranks and numbers of time delays. A practical estimate of the truncation rank was obtained from projection error analysis of the POD basis. Since the size of the operator matrices grows multiplicatively with the number of delays, relatively low truncation ranks were favored. Overall, truncation ranks in the range of 40-60, combined with a sufficiently large delay embedding, were found to be reasonable. The effect of time-delay embedding was examined by comparing models with no time delay and models with a delay length of $q = 100$. It is observed that including time-delay embedding improves the prediction of the system dynamics, with modest improvements corresponding to absolute reductions in the prediction error on the order of 0.01-0.1. It was also observed that sufficiently large time delays are required to obtain stable model fits. When small delay lengths are used, the fitting process can become unstable due to collinearity and rank deficiency arising from the use of consecutive snapshots. A potential avenue for future work could be the development of adaptive delay-selection strategies, in which the next snapshot to be stacked is chosen based on a criterion that reduces collinearity. Such an approach could improve stability while avoiding the need for excessively large operator sizes.

A combined-library DMDc approach, termed the *Multi-Operator Random Shuffling* method, was introduced. In this approach, all DMDc operators constructed from the signal library are projected

onto a common reduced basis. During prediction, a model is randomly selected at each time step to advance the system state. This approach was tested using a validation signal that is not present in the training library. The results show that the MORS model reduces the bias associated with individual models and yields predictions of lift, drag, and state evolution that balance the behaviors captured by the different operators.

Finally, the ROM was integrated into the *drlfoam* framework, replacing the high-fidelity CFD solver as the environment during training. It was observed that the averaged rewards did not improve over the course of the training episodes. Further analysis showed that, despite variations in the actuation input, the predicted lift and drag coefficients remained essentially unchanged. This behavior indicates that, in the present configuration, the DMDc-based ROM is largely insensitive to rapidly fluctuating actuation signals that arise during the early stages of training. In addition, the influence of the control operator \mathbf{B} may be small relative to the dominant dynamics governed by the unforced operator \mathbf{A} . These aspects require further investigation. As a consequence, the DRL agent is unable to learn a meaningful control policy within the current ROM-based training setup.

Outlook and future scope

If the observed lack of learning is indeed caused by the DMDc model's insufficient response to rapidly varying actuation inputs, one possible remedy is to decouple the control update rate from the ROM time-stepping. In the current setup, the control time step coincides with the DMDc roll-out time step, which means that a new angular velocity is sampled at every DMDc step. This may not allow sufficient time for the flow dynamics to respond meaningfully to a given actuation input. Increasing the control update interval could therefore enable the dynamics to develop more coherently. Alternatively, reducing the DMDc time step may allow the model to capture finer temporal dynamics, although this would come at increased computational cost. Both strategies require further investigation.

Another important direction for future work is the construction of a more robust library of DMDc models. Results presented in Sec. 5.3.2 already indicate that certain excitation signals, such as the chirp input, perform poorly when predicting force coefficients under qualitatively different validation signals. In contrast, more complex excitations, such as chirp signals with varying amplitude, which are fit on a richer set of flow dynamics, yield relatively improved predictive performance. This suggests that the training signals used to construct the DMDc library should be sufficiently diverse and complex to expose the model to a broad range of dynamical responses, particularly discontinuous or rapidly varying inputs, which are commonly encountered during the early stages of DRL training.

More generally, the present results indicate that it is difficult to construct a single DMDc model

that accurately captures the dynamics induced by all possible actuation inputs. As a consequence, adaptive strategies can be explored. One possible approach is to periodically retrain or update the DMDc model using high-fidelity CFD data, either at fixed intervals or when the ROM prediction error exceeds a prescribed threshold. Such an online or hybrid retraining strategy could significantly improve model accuracy and robustness, and may lead to effective integration of ROMs within closed-loop DRL frameworks.

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A. Appendix

A.1. Navier-Stokes equations for incompressible flow

Incompressible flow is governed by the Navier–Stokes equations, which in non-dimensional form can be written as

$$\nabla^* \cdot \mathbf{u}^* = 0, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}^*}{\partial t^*} + (\mathbf{u}^* \cdot \nabla^*) \mathbf{u}^* = -\nabla^* p^* + \frac{1}{Re} \nabla^{*2} \mathbf{u}^*. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

The first equation represents conservation of mass, and the second equation represents conservation of momentum.

The equations are non-dimensionalised using characteristic quantities of the flow, namely the cylinder diameter d and the free-stream velocity u_∞ . The corresponding non-dimensional variables are defined as

$$t^* = t \frac{u_\infty}{d}, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$\mathbf{u}^* = \frac{\mathbf{u}}{u_\infty}, \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$p^* = p \frac{d}{\mu u_\infty}, \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$\nabla^* = d \nabla. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

The superscript $(\cdot)^*$ denotes non-dimensional quantities. The Reynolds number associated with the flow is given by

$$Re = \frac{d u_\infty}{\nu}, \quad (\text{A.7})$$

where ν is the kinematic viscosity.

A.2. Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD)

A.2.1. DMD algorithm

In practical applications, the snapshot matrix is typically tall and skinny, since the state dimension m is large, making explicit construction of the full linear operator $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ infeasible. Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD) addresses this issue by projecting the dynamics onto a low-dimensional subspace and retaining only the dominant spectral components.

Given the snapshot matrices $\mathbf{X}', \mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times (n-1)}$, with $\text{rank}(\mathbf{X}) = r \leq n \ll m$, the least-squares approximation

$$\mathbf{Y} \approx \mathbf{A} \mathbf{X}' \quad (\text{A.8})$$

yields the operator $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{Y} \mathbf{X}'^\dagger$, which has rank at most r . Rather than forming \mathbf{A} explicitly, DMD operates on the reduced operator $\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$, obtained by projection onto the dominant left singular vectors of \mathbf{X} [1].

The DMD algorithm proceeds as follows:

1. Compute the truncated SVD of the snapshot matrix

$$\mathbf{X}' \approx \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_r \tilde{\mathbf{D}}_r \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_r^\top, \quad (\text{A.9})$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{U}}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times r}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{D}}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$, and $\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{(n-1) \times r}$. The truncation rank r is a hyperparameter chosen based on accuracy and computational cost.

2. The reduced linear operator is defined as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_r^\top \mathbf{Y} \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_r \tilde{\mathbf{D}}_r^{-1}. \quad (\text{A.10})$$

State evolution in reduced coordinates is given by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k, \quad (\text{A.11})$$

with reconstruction to the full state space via $\mathbf{x}_k \approx \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_r \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k$.

3. Compute the eigen-decomposition of the reduced operator

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \mathbf{S} = \mathbf{S} \mathbf{\Lambda}, \quad (\text{A.12})$$

where $\mathbf{\Lambda} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$ contains the DMD eigenvalues and $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$ the corresponding eigenvectors.

4. The high-dimensional DMD modes are reconstructed as

$$\mathbf{\Phi} = \mathbf{Y} \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_r \tilde{\mathbf{D}}_r^{-1} \mathbf{S}. \quad (\text{A.13})$$

Reconstruction

Using the truncated eigen-decomposition, the linear operator is approximated as

$$\mathbf{A} \approx \mathbf{\Phi}_r \mathbf{\Lambda}_r \mathbf{\Phi}_r^\dagger. \quad (\text{A.14})$$

The state at time step k is then given by

$$\mathbf{x}_k \approx \Phi_r \Lambda_r^{k-1} \Phi_r^\dagger \mathbf{x}_1. \quad (\text{A.15})$$

Defining the mode amplitudes $\mathbf{b}_r = \Phi_r^\dagger \mathbf{x}_1$, the reconstruction can be written as

$$\mathbf{x}_k \approx \sum_{i=1}^r b_i \phi_i \lambda_i^{k-1}, \quad (\text{A.16})$$

where ϕ_i and λ_i denote the i th DMD mode and eigenvalue, respectively.

Stacking the reconstructed snapshots yields

$$\mathbf{X} \approx \Phi_r \Gamma_b \mathbf{V}_\lambda, \quad (\text{A.17})$$

where $\Gamma_b = \text{diag}(\mathbf{b}_r)$ and \mathbf{V}_λ is the Vandermonde matrix constructed from the DMD eigenvalues.

A.3. Force coefficient evaluation

Listing A.1 shows the dictionary used to evaluate the lift and drag coefficients from the OpenFOAM fields.

```
FoamFile
{
  version 2.0;
  format ascii;
  class dictionary;
  object myDict;
}
functions
{
  forces_recon
  {
    type forceCoeffs;
    libs (forces);
    patches
    (
      cylinder
    );
    rhoInf 1;
    rho rhoInf;
    CofR (0.2 0.2 0.005);
    liftDir (0 1 0);
    dragDir (1 0 0);
    magUInf 1.0;
    lRef 0.1;
    Aref 0.001;
  }
}
```

Listing A.1: OpenFOAM dictionary used to evaluate lift and drag coefficients via `forceCoeffs`.

A.4. Mode coefficient plots for DMDc model-specific studies

This section presents the DMDc mode coefficient plots evaluated on the training and test datasets, as described in Sec. 5.2.1. Due to the large number of plots, only a few representative cases are shown for the random walk and the amplitude modulated signal. The complete set of plots is available in the GitHub repository [20].

Figure A.1.: Time evolution of the first five POD coefficients for the random-walk signal during the training interval without delay embedding ($q = 0$).

Figure A.2.: Time evolution of the first five POD coefficients for the random-walk signal during the testing interval without delay embedding ($q = 0$).

Figure A.3.: Time evolution of the first five POD coefficients for the random-walk signal during the training interval with delay embedding $q = 100$.

Figure A.4.: Time evolution of the first five POD coefficients for the random-walk signal during the testing interval with delay embedding $q = 100$.

Figure A.5.: Time evolution of the first five POD coefficients for the amplitude-modulated signal during the training interval without delay embedding ($q = 0$).

Figure A.6.: Time evolution of the first five POD coefficients for the amplitude-modulated signal during the testing interval without delay embedding ($q = 0$).

Figure A.7.: Time evolution of the first five POD coefficients for the amplitude-modulated signal during the training interval with delay embedding $q = 100$.

Figure A.8.: Time evolution of the first five POD coefficients for the amplitude-modulated signal during the testing interval with delay embedding $q = 100$.

A.5. Library of signals

This section presents data related to the library of signals. Figures A.9 and A.11 show the force coefficients obtained from the original CFD simulations for the respective actuation signals. Figure A.10 presents the projection error of the DMDc basis onto the augmented snapshot matrix.

Figure A.9.: Drag coefficients from the original simulation data of the library of signals

Figure A.10.: Projection error $E_{\text{proj, aug}}$ of the DMDc truncated basis on the time-delayed snapshot matrices. The error is computed using Eq. 5.13.

(a) Random walk

(b) Chirp

(c) Chirp with varying amplitude

(d) AM

Figure A.11.: Lift coefficients from the original simulation data of the library of signals